

**D3.4 Ecological toolkit (ESE1) for
MPAs prioritization and networking**

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prioritization and networking**

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	The Ecological Toolkit (ESE1) was developed to support the design, establishment and management of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) by improving decision-making processes, focusing on prioritisation of areas, integration of connectivity processes and assessment of human impacts on marine ecosystems. The ESE1 Ecological Toolkit, aligned with the ESE framework currently being developed in Task 4.4, provides a methodological guide to site-specific environmental assessment, as planned for WP5.
Abstract	The ESE1 Ecological Toolkit facilitates structured biodiversity conservation planning through four main practices: scoping, data collection and visualisation, analytical

diagnosis, and prioritisation and designation. The toolkit specifies the application of targeted methodologies, criteria and decision support tools (DSTs) to enhance evidence-based decision-making processes.

This initiative involved a detailed assessment of decision support tools (DSTs), their applications, and their refinement through integration with ecological data, hydrodynamic models and climate change considerations to effectively address pressures on marine ecosystems. By providing advanced ecological knowledge and incorporating nature-based solutions, the toolkit aims to support sustainable marine conservation strategies that recognise the challenges posed by climate change and human activities.

Alongside evaluating the functionality of existing tools, the task has made significant improvements to selected DSTs, in particular Tools4MSP and PlanWise4Blue (PW4B), focusing on cumulative effects assessment, prioritisation and adaptation to climate change. For Tools4MSP, enhancements include improved graphical interfaces for better functionality and usability, and a new climate

change pressure modelling module considering climate change rates. This model uses a nearest-neighbour approach to calculate analog-based velocities across the Mediterranean basin, a critical metric for climate adaptation planning. Although the results are preliminary, they highlight the potential of analog-based velocity calculations in adaptive management strategies for marine environments. The PW4B tool has been enriched by integrating HELCOM data layers, promoting synergy with HELCOM SPIA tool. The MSP4BIO project has also developed the Area-based Conservation Planner. This prioritisation tool, which is currently being tested, supports multiple conservation objectives and allows for customisable planning solutions. These developments improve conservation decision-making through a systematic and evidence-based approach.

The analysis highlighted that all of the identified tools offer applications that produce spatially explicit outputs. None of the identified tools could individually address all ecological and environmental dimensions, but integration of different tools is needed to ensure that DSTs

can provide more robust and ecologically meaningful insights that are essential for formulating adaptive management strategies in both MPA and MSP processes. By incorporating different tools into the various stages of MSP - from planning and design to implementation and management - stakeholders can better address ecological and environmental considerations, leading to more effective and sustainable management of marine resources. This approach not only enhances the resilience and health of marine ecosystems, but also supports the diverse objectives of different countries, taking into account their specific MSP maturity levels and environmental priorities. The report also informs potential users of the requirements for implementing the existing tools and those developed during the MSP4BIO project in both MPA and MSP processes.

However, in the spirit of 'not reinventing the wheel', it is important to continue to develop dynamic methods and interfaces to enhance the capabilities and ensure effective integration of existing DSTs, particularly in the areas of cumulative effects assessment, prioritisation

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	<p>and climate change response. Future efforts are needed to properly integrate functional connectivity into these tools, a critical aspect of comprehensive environmental planning and management, especially in the face of climate change. This integration will ensure that DSTs can provide more robust and ecologically meaningful insights for adaptive management strategies in both MPA and MSP processes.</p>
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Executive Summary

The Ecological Toolkit (ESE1) was developed to support the design, establishment and management of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) by improving decision-making processes, focusing on prioritisation of areas, integration of connectivity processes and assessment of human impacts on marine ecosystems. The ESE1 Ecological Toolkit, aligned with the ESE framework currently being developed in Task 4.4, provides a methodological guide to site-specific environmental assessment, as planned for WP5.

The ESE1 Ecological Toolkit facilitates structured biodiversity conservation planning through four main practices: scoping, data collection and visualisation, analytical diagnosis, and prioritisation and designation. The toolkit specifies the application of targeted methodologies, criteria and decision support tools (DSTs) to enhance evidence-based decision-making processes.

This initiative involved a detailed assessment of DSTs and their applications, and their refinement through integration with ecological data, hydrodynamic models and climate change considerations to effectively address pressures on marine ecosystems. By providing advanced ecological knowledge and incorporating nature-based solutions, the toolkit aims to support sustainable marine conservation strategies that recognise the challenges posed by climate change and human activities.

Alongside evaluating the functionality of existing tools, the task has made significant improvements to selected DSTs, in particular Tools4MSP and PlanWise4Blue (PW4B), focusing on cumulative effects assessment, prioritisation and adaptation to climate change. For Tools4MSP, enhancements include improved graphical interfaces for better functionality and usability, and a new climate change pressure modelling module considering climate change rates. This model uses a nearest-neighbour approach to calculate analog-based velocities across the Mediterranean basin, a critical metric for

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climate adaptation planning. Although the results are preliminary, they highlight the potential of analog-based velocity calculations in adaptive management strategies for marine environments. The PW4B tool has been enriched by integrating HELCOM data layers, promoting synergy with HELCOM SPIA tool. The MSP4BIO project has also developed the Area-based Conservation Planner. This prioritisation tool, which is currently being tested, supports multiple conservation objectives and allows for customisable planning solutions. These developments improve conservation decision-making through a systematic and evidence-based approach.

The analysis highlighted that all of the identified tools offer applications that produce spatially explicit outputs. None of the identified tools could individually address all ecological and environmental dimensions, but integration of different tools is needed to ensure that DSTs can provide more robust and ecologically meaningful insights that are essential for formulating adaptive management strategies in both MPA and Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) processes. By incorporating different tools into the various stages of MSP - from planning and design to implementation and management - stakeholders can better address ecological and environmental considerations, leading to more effective and sustainable management of marine resources. This approach not only enhances the resilience and health of marine ecosystems, but also supports the diverse objectives of different countries, taking into account their specific MSP maturity levels and environmental priorities. The report also informs potential users of the requirements for implementing the existing tools and those developed during the MSP4BIO project in both MPA and MSP processes.

However, in the spirit of 'not reinventing the wheel', it is important to continue to develop dynamic methods and interfaces to enhance the capabilities and ensure effective integration of existing DSTs, particularly in the areas of cumulative effects assessment, prioritisation and climate change response. Future efforts are needed to properly integrate

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functional connectivity into these tools, a critical aspect of comprehensive environmental planning and management, especially in the face of climate change. This integration will ensure that DSTs can provide more robust and ecologically meaningful insights for adaptive management strategies in both MPA and MSP processes.

1. Introduction

The appropriate design, effective establishment and management of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) are essential for conserving marine biodiversity and enhancing the resilience of marine ecosystems to a range of human and natural pressures. To achieve the above objectives, this deliverable introduces a comprehensive ecological toolkit, complemented by a thorough review and improvement of decision support tools (DSTs). These actions aim to refine decision-making processes for MPAs, with a focus on prioritising areas for protection, integrating connectivity processes, and assessing the impacts of human activities on marine ecosystems under current and future scenarios. The toolkit consists of an inventory of recommendations to competently guide decision-makers through the complex pathways of MPA prioritization and networking.

Building on the foundational outcomes of Tasks 3.1 and 3.2, which focused on refining ecological approaches and integrating climate change drivers into protection strategies, Task 3.3 focuses on improving science-based ecological and environmental tools to prioritize conservation areas. In addition, this task significantly enhances existing DSTs by integrating ecological data with relevant information from established data services (such as the Copernicus services) and hydrodynamic models. This comprehensive approach addresses ecological and environmental processes at both local and regional scales and addresses the multiple pressures on marine ecosystems, including those resulting from climate change. In the context of climate change adaptation, the toolkit includes specific references to Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), such as securing climate refugia.

The Task 3.3 undertook a comprehensive evaluation of spatially explicit DSTs to determine their ability to: (i) identify and prioritise ecologically or biologically significant areas (EBSAs); (ii) integrate connectivity processes; (iii) measure cumulative impacts of

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human activities; and (iv) assess ecological and environmental changes induced by climate change. The assessment generated relevant information on the potential applicability of the tools and necessary improvements for informing MPA processes. The identified DSTs, together with their underlying models and algorithms, were systematically classified according to their relevance along three main areas: (a) their purpose, covering a spectrum of applications from MPA establishment and expansion to ecosystem restoration and connectivity enhancement, including the development of blue-green corridors; (b) the type of protected area they relate to, distinguishing between fully protected and partially protected areas; and (c) their geographic applicability, covering coastal zones, continental shelves and deep-sea environments. The inventory also provided a summary of the key characteristics of the tools, models and algorithms, detailing their maturity, operability, uncertainty and compatibility for integration into Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP). It also identified the resources - both expertise and data - required for their effective implementation.

Tools4MSP, HELCOM CEA and PlanWise4Blue were refined in several dimensions based on the information gathered in the assessment. For example, dispersion models have been fine-tuned to mimic ecological connectivity features more accurately and to manage the distribution of pollutants and marine debris. A meta-analytic approach was used to translate scientific evidence into basic knowledge on human pressures with more localized impacts, such as industrial fishing and wind farm construction. These refined models and algorithms were then seamlessly integrated into the tools. This integration enables robust human and climate change impact assessments on environmental and biodiversity features while also providing support for what-if scenario analysis.

Finally, the Ecological Toolkit (ESE1) has been rigorously developed to promote improved decision-making firmly rooted in the most up-to-date and advanced ecological knowledge. Combining newly defined prioritization criteria and the practical use of DSTs at test sites,

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the toolkit fits seamlessly into WP4, where the general ESE framework is developed as an interconnected system of different modules each representing ecological, social and economic dimensions. This detailed integration of ecological and environmental components and strategies, encapsulated in ESE1, is designed to enhance the ability to identify critical ecological attributes, assess the environmental consequences of local and transboundary pressures, acknowledge inherent uncertainties and confidently assess the effectiveness of prospective management approaches and blue growth scenarios. This strategic pooling of information and resources aims to streamline decision-making processes and ensure that they are informed and conducive to the sustainability and conservation of marine ecosystems. As such, the report provides a methodological blueprint for conducting site-specific environmental assessments, as foreseen in WP5.

2. Methods

2.1 Ecological toolkit (ESE1) conceptual model

ESE1, also referred to as the Ecological Toolkit, improves decision-making processes for MPAs by helping to prioritise protected areas, integrate connectivity processes and assess the impacts of human activities on marine ecosystems for both current and future scenarios. The toolkit provides a range of solutions and a comprehensive step-by-step guide to help decision-makers navigate the complex processes of MPA prioritisation and connectivity. ESE1 integrates a set of operational and enhanced ecological and climate-related criteria derived from systematic reviews and desktop analyses as outlined in WP2 (D2.2) and WP3 (D3.2 and D3.3). It also includes guidance on incorporating climate change scenarios into protection and prioritisation strategies for the development of climate-smart MPAs, as detailed in WP3, D3.3. This comprehensive approach will ensure that MPAs are designed and managed with the latest ecological knowledge and climate resilience principles. Based on a curated set of ecological criteria, this guide guides through the essential steps of vulnerability assessment for prioritising conservation actions in MPAs. It provides methodologies that equip stakeholders with the tools to develop conservation scenarios that are resilient to climate change.

Ultimately, ESE1 provides science-based ecological and environmental tools for prioritising protected areas. By integrating ecological data with relevant insights from existing Copernicus services and hydrodynamic models, this module significantly enhances current DSTs. It effectively addresses ecological and environmental processes at local and regional scales, addressing the multiple pressures on marine ecosystems, including the impacts of climate change. The Ecological toolkit includes the following spatially explicit Decision Support Tools: Cumulative Effects Assessment (CEA) tools,

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Climate Change impact Assessment Tools and Prioritization Tools (these tools also incorporate connectivity aspects).

2.2 Overview on ecological and climate-related criteria

The ESE1 contains a wide range of both abiotic and biotic criteria, including specific characteristics of species and habitats required for conservation planning. This section covers biotic criteria, i.e., those that relate to living organisms, habitats, ecosystems and their genetic composition, as well as factors related to climate impacts, change and mitigation on these living entities. It also covers their vulnerability and resilience, highlighting their capacity to adapt and recover from the effects of climate change. These criteria were synthesised from comprehensive reviews of the scientific literature, analyses of grey literature, document searches and desktop studies carried out under Tasks 2.2, 3.1 and 3.2. Task 2.2 categorized and compiled lists of criteria, spanning from biotic to abiotic, socio ecological and ecological status criteria, already recognised in official national and international documents and initiatives (D2.2). Tasks 3.1 and 3.2 focus and extended these criteria to include functional aspects that are often overlooked in conservation planning (D3.2) and provided an updated step-by-step guide for addressing climate change and its effects in Area-Based Management Tools (ABMTs) (D3.3). The ecological/biotic criteria from D2.2 were primarily subdivided into three categories; structural (focusing on ecosystem, habitat and species structure, e.g., species presence, diversity and habitat complexity), functional (addressing ecosystem functions and processes) and genetic (relating to the genetic diversity of organisms). D2.2 also introduced criteria related to ecological status, which encompasses the condition or state of ecological features and the environment, including aspects of ecological integrity, conservation status, naturalness and the level of disturbance affecting specific ecological features, all of which could inform the ESE1 framework. In this deliverable we explain the process of integrating ecological criteria into ESE1, starting with conservation and

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management needs and issues. The integration of criteria into ESE1 begins with the first phase of the ESE1 toolkit, called 'scoping'. During this phase, we provide a concise guide to refining management questions that may initially appear too broad. This process involves distilling these questions into specific keywords, such as those that highlight conservation issues and ecological features. These keywords will facilitate linking to relevant sub-categories and macro-criteria as described in section 3.2.1.

2.3 Assessment of existing spatially explicit decision support tools: identified capabilities and needed developments

The second step involved a comprehensive desktop assessment of promising spatially explicit DSTs. The methodology is based on an analytical framework developed by decision support software developers and managers. This framework has been specifically tailored to analyse tools designed to facilitate a range of processes, including the management of MSP and MPA initiatives in European seas (Depellegrin et al., 2021). These tools, which are capable of systematically assessing the ecological and environmental characteristics of marine ecosystems and conducting alternative scenario analyses, were evaluated for their characteristics, maturity and operability in identifying and prioritizing EBSAs. The performed assessment provided critical insights into the efforts required to merge and enhance existing DSTs, incorporating the concepts and criteria defined in T3.1 and T3.2, and to skilfully inform MPA and MSP processes.

The conceptual framework for the assessment included an evaluation of the primary objectives of each DST. These objectives ranged from facilitating communication between the scientific community and managers, to supporting ecosystem-based management, to conducting scenario analysis. The purposes of the DSTs were also examined, including environmental impact assessment, conflict analysis, data collection, governance support and scenario-based analysis. The assessment identified the developers of these tools, including national research and academic institutions, as well

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as other collaborating institutions, their types and roles. The target users of these tools were identified, including national planning authorities, academia, regional decision-makers and NGOs. In addition, the assessment looked at the sources of funding for these tools, including EU, national or private funding, and strategies for their long-term sustainability beyond the life of the project.

From a technical point of view, the tools were categorized according to their application type, such as web-based or desktop applications. The underlying programming languages, software frameworks and the functionalities of their graphical user interfaces were assessed. The availability of documentation, guidelines and the presence of active user and developer communities were also key points of evaluation. The portability of the tools, the types of input data, their sources and accessibility were also examined.

The assessment also focused on the types of geospatial models used by these tools, such as CEA and Maritime Use Conflict Analysis. It examined the definition of CEA within each DST and how their algorithms differed from standard models. The inclusion of impact chain components and the provision of sensitivity scores were also evaluated.

Finally, the empirical evaluation of the tools included identifying the stages of the MSP process where each DST can be used. Information was gathered on whether and how the DSTs are being introduced into national/regional MSP processes. The communication of uncertainty in knowledge, data and model results and the level of stakeholder involvement were also key points of evaluation. The effectiveness of the tools in communicating results to stakeholders was a critical aspect of the assessment. This structured approach provided a comprehensive understanding of the capabilities, limitations and suitability of each DST for specific applications in marine ecosystem management and planning.

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2.4 Approaches for modelling and IT development

Modelling and IT needs were identified and developed to support and extend the capabilities of the DSTs. These developments included improving the underlying models and algorithms and web-based solutions to ensure they could effectively support practitioners in establishing and expanding MPAs, identifying priority areas for restoration, and strengthening connectivity between MPAs through strategically located blue-green corridors.

The modelling and IT development needs to support practitioners in establishing and expanding MPAs, identifying priority areas for restoration, and improving connectivity between MPAs through strategically located blue-green corridors are many and complex.

A key development requirement is the creation of an advanced CEA tool. This tool is designed to harness a wide range of scientific evidence and facilitate a thorough analysis of ecological impacts that goes beyond reliance on expert knowledge alone. It is adept at quantifying the environmental impacts of different human use scenarios, whether existing or projected for the future. By effectively reducing these impacts, the tool plays a key role in the development of sustainable planning solutions.

Another major need for further development is the operationalization of a new generation of prioritisation tools that take into account both the integrity of nature and the costs associated with establishing protected areas. Integrating of this prioritisation tool with the developed CEA tool is critical. Such integration will help to avoid scenarios where MPAs are designated in areas of high human pressure, which could compromise the objectives of MPAs.

To improve accessibility and usability, there is a need to share these tools through web platforms. This approach requires the development of big data analysis capabilities and the optimization of analysis processes. Simplifying the graphical presentation of data and ensuring interoperability by uploading and downloading key file formats are also essential

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steps. These improvements will make the tools more user-friendly and facilitate wider adoption by practitioners.

2.5 Assessing data availability for the implementation of models and tools

The data availability required to implement improved DSTs in the case study sites (CS) was systematically assessed. To do so, we used the information gathered on available data platforms, tools and models performed by T2.1, and formal requests were sent to the CS leaders and T5.1 ("Gap analysis at test sites to support knowledge-based MSP") to identify data availability and gaps. Strategic collaborations were established with local data managers where data infrastructure was readily available at CS sites. In particular, a bilateral partnership between UTARTU and HELCOM was established for the effective transfer and operationalisation of HELCOM data that is relevant to MPA processes and MSP for the implementation of the ESE1 toolkit in the Baltic Sea. The aim was to ensure the effective use of the data infrastructure for the subsequent implementation of DSTs.

2.6 Scale of analysis

The scale of analysis spanned the CS, sub-basin and sea basin levels, with specific dependencies on the nature of the CS sites considered (e.g., the Baltic CS, which covers the entire basin) and the available data across the different European sea basins.

These methodological steps have combined scientific knowledge and practical tools and synthesized them into the Ecological Toolkit (ESE1). This toolkit, underpinned by advanced ecological knowledge and technological frameworks, aims to significantly improve MPA prioritization and networking processes, ensuring that they are data-driven, effective and holistically informed by nuanced ecological and environmental criteria.

3. Ecological toolkit (ESE1)

3.1 ESE1 in the context of the ESE management framework

The ESE1 Ecological Toolkit is structured around a step-by-step methodology, in line with the conceptual model of the ESE framework, currently being developed in Task 4.4 and then used in WP5. The main elements (guiding principles) of the ESE framework are illustrated in Figure 3.1. The initiation of the ESE framework is driven by the identification of management needs and issues at the site level. Specifically, for ESE1, the focus is on those needs and questions that are predominantly environmental in nature. Depending on the specific nature of the need or question, the toolkit provides detailed guidance on how to use the criteria and tools that have been carefully reviewed and organised during the activities of WP3. In line with the terminology used in the ESE framework, these instructions are referred to as practices and are presented as concise guidance documents.

Figure 3.1. Guiding elements of the ESE management framework.

The ESE framework is structured around the following key practices, derived from the categorisation of management needs and questions gathered from the project's test sites:

1. Scoping
2. Data collection and presentation
3. Analysis and diagnosis
4. Prioritisation and designation
5. Management implementation
6. Monitoring and evaluation
7. Stakeholder engagement and consultation

Each practice responds to a specific need and addresses the use of *ad hoc* criteria and tools. In an MSP/MPA planning process, practices are linked through a sequential, step-by-step approach.

The ESE1 provides a functional description of the first four practices: 1) Scoping, 2) Data collection and presentation, 3) Analysis and Diagnosis and 4) Prioritization and Designation. These four practices are critical to improving biodiversity conservation in planning efforts. These descriptions are tailored to cover content related to ecological aspects. Within the evolving ESE framework (currently being developed as part of Task 4.4), the outlines of these four practices will be enriched with contributions from ESE2 and additional tools, alongside the inclusion of the remaining practices.

Each practice is structured around the following components:

- Aim of the practice
- Steps required for implementation
- Identification of relevant criteria (or clusters of criteria)
- Selection of metrics and methodologies corresponding to these criteria
- Identification of necessary and accessible data

In the following sections, the Ecological Toolkit is detailed by elaborating on the descriptions of the four key practices. The practices illustrate how to use ecological

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criteria and tools to support identification, designation and prioritization of area-based measures addressing biodiversity conservation. In this way, the results of all the tasks within WP3 are structured into a practical workflow that supports decision making.

3.2 ESE1 logic and structure

The conceptual flow of the Ecological Toolkit (Figure 3.2) originates from the management questions and needs identified at test-site level. Table A1 in Appendix A presents some of the needs and questions identified in the MSP4BIO project test cases and collected in the framework of various tasks (see D4.1, D5.1, D5.2). The table helps sequentially linking each of the questions to subsequent ESE1 practices (step-by-step approach). The type of question determines the methodology (and the degree of complexity) of the ecological analysis to be undertaken with the support of the Ecological Toolkit. If the question only requires basic knowledge information, then Practice 1 – Scoping alone will be sufficient to provide answers. However, if the focus of the question is on management issues, such as designing a protected area within MSP or considering climate change scenarios, the process will progress from Practice 1 to 4. Each practice provides specific guidance and indicates which (and how) ecological criteria (including those related to climate change) and spatially explicit DSTs can be applied to support the process.

Figure 3.2. Structure of the Ecological toolkit.

3.2.1 Ecological criteria in ESE1

Based on the integration of the results from WP2 (D2.2) and WP3 (D3.2 and D3.3), the Ecological Toolkit (ESE1) considers the following definitions and hierarchical categorization for ecological criteria:

Criterion. A standard or principle for prioritizing and managing conservation areas, and for designing and evaluating the effectiveness of conservation measures. Some examples of criteria are the protection of feeding grounds of endangered predators; areas/habitats essential for the development of the life cycle of keystone species;

areas/habitats essential for the maintenance of genetic diversity hotspots (e.g., needed to ensure adaptation in the context of climate change).

Indicator. Direct measurement or proxy of relevant biotic or abiotic components/processes used to implement and assess the criteria.

The ESE1 is based on the “Ecological and genetic criteria” category, as defined in D2.2 (Table 6, category 1), which collects all criteria that relate to living organisms, habitats and ecosystems, and their respective genetic structure. This category is subdivided into two sub-categories:

1.1 “*Functional*” criteria subcategory that considers the processes and properties of ecosystems and their components that are related to their functioning, from ecosystem level to species level (e.g., life traits, biological traits capturing inter-specific interactions and the connections between species and their environment, to the capacity to adapt/ability to recover from direct human activities, climate change, or natural disasters).

1.2 “*Structural*” criteria subcategory that includes criteria that refer to the structure of ecosystems, habitats and species, i.e., which species are there and how many, how complex is the habitat (e.g., species composition, species stratification, distributional pattern/range/distribution changes, among others).

Apart from these, D2.2 lists in category 1 also the subcategories 1.3 genetic, and 1.4 ecological status, and categories 2, 3 and 4 (abiotic, anthropogenic and climate criteria, respectively) which are of relevance for the toolkit, but will not be the focus of this deliverable. The complete broad categorization/subcategorization of criteria categories, sub-categories and their keywords has been defined in Annex A of D2.2.

In WP3 a deeper focus has been made on the criteria subcategory 1.1 “functional” for improved functional criteria (D3.2) and climate change (D3.3) related ecological criteria.

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To complement and further detail the above-mentioned category and sub-categories, ESE1 identifies several conservation-supporting macro-criteria, these are broad criteria groups that support the identification of important ecological structural and functional features of the ecosystems. Macro-criteria can guide the identification, designation and prioritization of area-based management tools. Operatively, they feed the ESE1 practices, as described below.

The criteria (and keywords) related to conservation macro-criteria which are used to identify and prioritize areas/species on the base of their intrinsic natural value - such as areas that contain unique or rare habitats and/or species, contain restricted range/endemic species, distinct, good representativeness of habitats, iconic species, etc. - are listed under Subcategory 1.2: Structural criteria and reported in Annex I, of deliverable D2.2.

In this deliverable we focus mainly on functional macro-criteria emerged from the analysis provided under D3.2 and D3.3, incorporating elements of D2.2.

Conservation macro-criteria which are used to identify and prioritize areas/species from the functional point of view include:

1. Fragile and sensitive habitats and/or species of concern for conservation, at risk of extinction, sensitive/vulnerable to climate and non-climate pressures (i.e., vulnerability);
2. Important habitat/species for the integrity and stability of ecosystem functioning (i.e., stability);
3. Hotspots of ecosystem functioning and functional diversity (i.e., functional hotspots);

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4. Areas important for the completion of life cycles: nursery, feeding, spawning, breeding, ecological corridors-connectivity among areas, etc. (i.e., life cycle critical areas);

5. Areas/communities/species with climate change adaptive, mitigation, resilience potential (i.e., climate-smart potential).

D3.2 lists four clusters of functional criteria terms emerged from the literature screening: biological traits, trophic ecology, functional diversity, connectivity, i.e., broad ecological topics or themes supporting the evaluation of ecological properties used as criteria for identification, prioritization and designation of area-based management tools. Here we nested D3.2 criteria terms and criteria clusters and D3.3 criteria to fit the five functional macro-criteria defined above.

In the following sections, functional macro-criteria are briefly described. A graphical representation of macro-criteria feeding the practices of the Ecological Toolkit and its structure is presented in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3. ESE1 – Ecological criteria feeding into the Ecological Toolkit ESE1 practices.

3.2.1.1 Ecological macro-criteria: vulnerability

Vulnerability: this macro-criterion is based on four criteria - sensitivity, resistance, resilience/recovery and adaptivity which can, depending on the case be described in a more specific way. For example, Vulnerability can currently only be linked to Sensitivity regarding the acceptable level of uncertainty and the scope of the management question (see D3.3 for climate vulnerability). This macro-criterion is mainly based on biological traits and species distribution analysis. Traits represent morphological, biochemical, physiological, structural, phenological, behavioural, and ecological characteristics of organisms, whether individuals or species which shape their ecological performance

(Cadotte et al., 2011, and literature within section 3.2.1 in D3.2), i.e., their effects on ecosystem functioning and ability to survive and reproduce. Therefore, species traits are directly linked to sensitivity to human stressors as well as climatic drivers. Traits determine resistance, adaptivity and even ecological connectivity (movement capacity, number of offspring, etc.) at population and community levels (see for example Tables 7-9 in D3.3). Another approach is related to assessing vulnerability of food webs (such as, e.g., assessing the risk of fishery-induced trophic cascading effects).

The main uses of the vulnerability macro-criterion in conservation are:

1. Set conservation priority (i.e., assessing and predicting the vulnerability of species and communities to human-made impacts and climate change), as well as forecasting species extinction risks and evaluating community velocities (i.e., future projection of species distribution);
2. Design more defined boundary for protection, design cross-boundary MPAs when stressors are dispersed;
3. Identify stable, climate-smart potential (areas that promote mitigation and adaptation under climate change) or highly vulnerable areas;
4. Monitor the effectiveness of area-based management tools and to develop scenarios for their adaptive management, e.g., reserve effect or measuring fishery-induced trophic cascades due to overfishing (see D3.2);
5. Create monitoring programme of MPAs measuring climate incidence, species and areas resilience and adaptivity (involves the ongoing assessment of the biological traits of species over time to effectively trace the impacts of management interventions).

Cases of application of this macro-criterion and criteria keywords to assess sensitivity through biological traits are reported in paragraph 3.2.1 and Table 3 in D3.2 and detailed

for assessing sensitivity to climate change drivers in D3.3. Table 10 in D3.3 lists a selection of traits that respond to climatic and non-climatic stressors.

3.2.1.2 Ecological macro-criteria: stability

Stability: this macro-criterion reflects the ability of communities to fill diverse niches, assimilate energy (productivity), transfer it within and across ecosystems, and enhance and stabilize ecosystem processes (functioning). Inner stability criteria are redundancy (e.g., the same function provided by several species with different levels of vulnerability), ecosystem integrity and adaptivity (e.g., the higher the level of functional diversity, the higher the probability of a system to adapt to new conditions). Therefore, this macro-criterion is mainly supported by functional diversity matrices (for an extended definition see paragraph 3.2.2 in D3.2). Connectivity is also essential to maintain stability, persistence, and adaptation (paragraph 3.2.4 in D3.2).

An extended list of terms/keywords and examples of application of this macro-criteria are reported in Figure 2 and Table 4 in D3.2.

The main uses of the stability macro-criterion are:

1. Identifying priority areas where to improve conservation in relation to climatic and non-climatic threats;
2. Optimizing site selection and spatial conservation strategies by providing scenarios (including functional diversity other than species diversity as a benchmark for definition of diversity hotspot) and optimization of sites (or habitats) selection for protection;
3. Evaluating timing for which the management measures implemented in the area will be efficient.

3.2.1.3 Ecological macro-criteria: functional hotspots

Functional hotspots: This macro-criterion refers to areas that are important for the provision of a discrete ecological function (e.g., Carbon storage, photosynthetic production) or areas where key ecological functions are concentrated (e.g., productivity). Internal criteria for functional hotspots are the presence of key functional species (e.g., apex predators, primary producers or other specific trophic group, functionally rare species, Grenié et al., 2018), key functional areas (e.g., Carbon sink and source areas), functionally representative areas (areas with many critical/key functions) and food web structure (complexity, length, interactions). The strategy for addressing functional hotspots is mainly based on functional diversity and trophic ecology approaches and metrics.

The main uses of functional hotspots in conservation planning are:

1. Assessing areas of high productivity that can also serve as food sources for other areas (including as a prerequisite for designating MPA networks);
2. Assessing essential/critical functions in protected areas (functional representativeness and uniqueness);
3. Potential proxy for ecosystem adaptive capacity.

3.2.1.4 Ecological macro-criteria: life cycle critical areas

Life cycle critical areas: This macro-criterion corresponds to the need for organisms to move between vital (critical) areas in order to fulfil their vital functions and complete their life cycle. It therefore refers to areas important for the completion of the life cycle of organisms (nursery, feeding, spawning, breeding) and the ecological corridors - links between these areas, etc. Criteria within this macro-criterion include ecological corridors/migration routes, steppingstone areas, refuge areas, larval sources and spawning aggregation areas, nursery and breeding areas, recruitment areas (larval

sinks), development and feeding/foraging habitats/areas. A possible methodological strategy to address this macro-criterion is the modelling of species and habitat distributions and ecological connectivity.

The main uses of the macro-criterion life cycle critical areas in conservation planning are:

1. Reshaping/enlarging of MPAs to provide self-seeding sources/supply;
2. Delineating management units across the range and prioritizes areas within management units based on current and future conditions under various scenarios of climate change and human impacts.
3. Reconciling natural species' range with different area-based management tools boundaries and scope (e.g., identifying management units, home ranges for mobile species through also coordination among management entities, MPAs, marine parks, etc., to effectively protect a species life cycle);
4. Planning networks of protected areas (identification of new potential areas);
5. Connecting isolated areas if necessary and those critical to life cycles.

3.2.1.5 Ecological macro-criteria: climate-smart potential

Climate-smart potential: This macro-criterion focuses on identifying areas and species that offer significant climate benefits, such as contributing to climate mitigation protection and restoration, enhancing ecosystem and community resilience, and facilitating adaptation to climate change. The assessment of climate-smart potential is based on evaluating biodiversity vulnerability to current and future climate change impacts, alongside the analysis of climate velocities. This macro-criterion is supported by several specific criteria outlined in section 5.1.1 of D3.3, including the "Concentrative Potential of Species of Climatic Interest" (which, although largely theoretical, has been empirically demonstrated in some species for their recovery/resilience or adaptability to climate change), "Potential for Mitigation" (for example, through carbon sequestration and acidity

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buffering, as discussed by Jacquemont et al., 2022), "Potential for Adaptation", "Connectivity Potential", and "Climatic Stability" (which encompasses both dynamic stability and climate-refugia).

The main uses of the climate-smart potential macro-criterion in conservation planning are:

1. Identifying of climate-smart areas and or key species;
2. Evaluating of mitigation and adaptation potential inside a management entity;
3. Evaluating of the potential future productivity of areas of interest under climate change and climate change incidence on local communities (e.g., in the context of fisheries planning);
4. Evaluating local risks (e.g., food supply);
5. Informing the design of MPAs and MPA networks (D3.3, section 6).

3.3 Steps in the implementation of ESE1

In this section, we look in more detail at the ESE1 framework, outlining the steps (Figure 3.4) and illustrating the macro-criteria, criteria and indicators with theoretical examples. We present the data requirements and potential tools for addressing the issues outlined, setting the stage for the following sections where these tools and their development are discussed in detail.

The ESE1 pre-identifies the environmental macro-criteria together with potential methodological strategies to be analysed in the following practices. In Practice 1 - Scoping, the macro criteria and criteria are linked to the keywords of the questions, the prioritised/selected ecological objective, the scoping boundaries of the questions (if addressing the MPA or MSP scale) and the area. This will guide the identification of data needs in Practice 2 - Data and analyses. In Practice 3 - Analysis and diagnosis, macro-criteria and criteria are re-evaluated depending on data availability, and the spatial and temporal scale.

Figure 3.4. Steps of implementation of ESE1.

3.3.1 Practice 1 - Scoping

Aim of the practice: This step is designed to identify and gather all relevant information that is essential for a thorough understanding of the study context, as initially outlined by the management needs or questions. It serves as a critical step in recognising all key elements, and acts in part as a prioritisation exercise, selecting only those elements that are truly important. This approach helps to accurately define the ecological and management scope and boundaries of the study area.

Starting with management questions, the scoping process aims to refine and focus such questions in case their elements are not fully and clearly defined. Initially, conservation or

management needs should be translated into precise management questions - a critical step that, while not covered in this deliverable, will be thoroughly explored within the broader ESE framework. Table A1 in Appendix A presents some of the stakeholder needs, questions and issues identified in the MSP4BIO project test cases and collected in the framework of various tasks (see D4.1, D5.1, D5.2). Starting from the original stakeholder needs, questions have been rephrased to provide practical and informative management questions. Each question is sequentially linked to subsequent ESE1 practices. This table also includes notes on refining and guiding the scoping process, underlining its critical role as a preparatory step for the subsequent practices.

In the Scoping practice, questions are deconstructed and examined according to essential thematic elements, which are outlined and summarised in this guidance. This step is also connected to and extends some elements of step 1 “setting the assessment” of the guidance for building climate change scenarios for protection strategies presented in chapter 2 of D3.3.

Table A2 in this deliverable provides illustrative examples of the ESE1 scoping elements, which include:

- *The main theme of the question.* Identifies generic keywords within the question, such as climate change, sensitivity to human impacts, connectivity, vulnerable marine ecosystems, pelagic species, etc.
- *Definition of management objective.* Specifies the management objective, e.g., the design of a new MPA, expansion of an existing MPA, management of existing MPAs or design of a network of MPAs.
- *Context scale.* Determines whether the scope is at MSP or MPA level.
- *Definition of spatial and temporal scale.* The temporal scale is particularly important in the context of climate change, spanning decades to centuries, while the spatial scale depends on the conservation objective, whether it is focused on

one or more MPAs, networks of MPAs, at sub-national, national or transboundary scales (for a more detailed definition and guidance on selecting spatial and temporal scales, see section 2.3 in D3.3).

- *Geographical area.* Defines the geographical boundaries or sea basin, possibly delimited by geographical coordinates (latitude and longitude, if available).
- *Temporal scale.* Directly influences the choice of climatic and non-climatic stressors (number and intensity) and the choice of projection, but also the degree of uncertainty of the analysis, and depends on the life cycle of the management target and the management objective. This step is extremely important if the management question already has a spatially limited target in its objectives.
- *Ecological approach.* Clarifies whether the approach is area-based, species-based or a combination of both.
- *Management approach suggested by the question.* The approach is defined here as either conservative, i.e., applying strict protection based on current scientific and empirical knowledge and limiting the impact of uncertainty on the effectiveness of protection (e.g., promoting the conservation of the list of vulnerable species), or selective, i.e., more pragmatic, taking into account the limited means of ensuring ecological protection and the difficulty of making management trade-offs between conservation and human activities, particularly in heavily used coastal areas (e.g., conserve 75% of the species most likely to survive in an area, conserve flagship species, among others). A detailed and precautionary definition of conservation priorities should be made with the help of scientific experts or on the basis of existing policies, such as the Habitats and Species Directive (HD) or the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). A detailed analysis of this step is provided in D3.3 guide, section 2.2.
- *Bio-ecological target specification.* Identify the elements of priority for conservation, from individual species to ecosystem level, based on the scope and

geographical area of the question, specifying the target as precisely as possible (e.g., Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems - VME, whales, Posidonia meadows) and the species level where available (e.g., *Eunicella cavolinii*). Elements to support decision making in the face of climate change can be found in the D3.3 guide.

- *Criteria to prioritize species/ecosystems for conservation.* This step defines the identification of conservation priorities, supported by the lists of species/habitat priority conservation criteria at global, European and regional levels and clustered at the level of geographical regions, as reported in D2.2 (Table 9, Annex 2). Detailed guidance on how to prioritise ecological elements and related criteria is also reported in D3.3, section 2.5. For example, the potential for resistance, recovery or adaptation of species or areas are new elements that should be considered when selecting species or areas of interest for the development of climate-smart management measures, MPAs and MPA networks. The Table 2 in D3.3 reports a step-by-step process, modified from Swan et al. (2017), for identifying key species. The most common strategy is risk or threat assessment (Le Berre et al., 2019). The Red Lists assess the extinction risk of species (IUCN, 2012) and are therefore not intended as a priority list for species conservation. In addition to extinction risk as an important reason for conservation, biogeographical, financial and cultural factors should also be taken into account. Another strategy is based on vulnerability to specific threats due to climate change and/or human activities. Apart from threats and vulnerability, other approaches can be based on conservation concerns (intrinsic value of species, e.g., rarity or local distribution and endemism, national importance, genetic or taxonomic uniqueness, phylogenetic distinctiveness) or value of resources or ecosystem services (economic value, attractive species, cultural importance) or ecological distinctiveness (e.g., ecological range, functional role, keystone species, propagation potential, La Berre et al., 2019). The D3.3 reports three criteria for

species prioritization under climate change, that can be extended for general species prioritization: (1) Services criteria (role that the species deliver to human, including social and economic indicators, generally ranked by the users themselves (D4.1), (2) Ecological criteria (role that the species exerts in the environment and trophic networks that could also be linked to species traits, D2.2 and D3.2) and (3) Climatic/non-climatic criteria linked to species sensitivity (including resistance, recovery and adaptive potential) link to their inner traits (see D3.3).

The three rankings will provide a final score that could highlight the species to prioritize regarding the creation of management patterns. This ranking system needs to be defined and is outside the scope of this deliverable.

- *Macro-criteria and potential methodological strategies (to be analysed in the following practices)*. In this step macro-criteria are indicated depending on the other defined scoping steps, and methodological approaches are suggested. This step also guides practices 2-4. When a macro-criterion is identified in the scoping, a selection of inner criteria and suggested methodological strategies will follow (e.g., for vulnerability, cf. section 3.1.2).
 - *Vulnerability* inner criteria: BOX 1 gives an example of the selection of criteria and characteristics based on a test site question (scoping section). The method is chosen according to the desired spatio-temporal scale of the analysis (mobilisation of climatic stressors, temporal boundaries), the type of output expected (e.g., qualitative or quantitative), and the level of expertise/complexity of the model for analysis performance and result evaluation (from an ecological and analytical point of view) (D3.3, section 3.4). In ESE1, we promote the use of a mixed approach based on species distribution and trait-based vulnerability assessment, so that we can consider this parameter as the default choice of the model. In this case, a list of traits needs to be defined. In terms of internal

- criteria, vulnerability could be summarised in sensitivity criteria or include potential mechanistic and evolutionary response criteria (e.g., resistance, adaptation, recovery). The choice of internal criteria to include in an analysis depends on the management question, the climatic inclusion (as vulnerability may include both climatic and non-climatic stressors or only a subset of them), the accepted level of uncertainty in the analysis, and the timing of future projections. Regarding climate change, the responses of organisms or communities are rarely assessed (especially in the field), whereas models are employed to project species distribution across various future scenarios. The number of criteria selected modifies the complexity of the equation linked to the macro-criterion and increases the number of traits to be included in the analysis. Traits are selected for each criterion (sensitivity, resistance, adaptation, resistance/recovery) based on five sub-criteria: "Uniqueness of information", "Stressor selection and importance", "Temporal scale of projection", "Selected climatic scenario" and "Ecological level" (D3.3, section 3.2.2). A list of features by ecological level (e.g., area, community, species) (D3.3, section 3.3.2) and associated databases are provided in D3.3.
- *Stability* inner criteria (redundancy, ecosystem integrity and adaptive capacity): can be analysed through functional diversity, by assessing and comparing vulnerability to potential pressures, and by measuring ecological connectivity, as these are all essential for maintaining stability, persistence and adaptability. Examples of vulnerability assessment approaches have been described in the previous section. Different methodological approaches and metrics for functional diversity are described in sections 3.2.2.3 and 3.2.2.4 of D3.2. Species composition indices (richness, evenness) based on species occurrences, can be used as proxies for functional diversity, although in several cases species richness patterns are incongruent with functional and

phylogenetic diversity, indicating the important contribution of functional traits and evolutionary diversity to conservation planning (Albouy et al., 2017; Tan et al., 2022). Functional diversity indices are obtained by analysing species traits (functional trait composition, number of functional traits in a selected habitat/area, etc.). Among the different functional diversity indices, functional richness (FRic; Villéger et al., 2008) is considered a more reliable approach. It is calculated as the volume of the convex hull of all included traits. It requires the availability of species and species trait data. Approaches combining species and functional composition can be used (Bevilacqua and Terlizzi, 2020).

- *Functional hot spots* inner criteria: are characterised by the presence of key functional species, critical functional areas, functionally representative areas and food web structure. The methodological approach to identifying these hotspots ranges from looking at functional diversity to using trophic ecology methods. For example, functional rarity can be assessed and quantified by comparing the distinctiveness of species' trait values with those of other species in the pool and its geographical range relative to the extent of the study area. Assessing functions such as primary and secondary production rates and Carbon storage potential is one strategy for identifying areas of high functional value. In addition, community data - such as diversity, species composition, abundance, biomass and distribution - provide other relevant insights. Individual characteristics such as size are relevant. Size is a critical parameter that can help extrapolate metrics such as secondary production from the individual to the community level. The structural properties of food webs may indicate key species, while dietary composition indicates prey importance. Some marine taxa diet databases are available (e.g., Fishbase, SeaLifeBase, DAPSTOM, Food Habits Database, MesopTroph) as well as databases on

trophic markers (e.g., MarTurtSI, SCAR). Large volumes of relevant data remain scattered in the literature or unpublished, making it difficult and laborious to find and reuse (D3.2).

- *Critical areas in the life cycle* inner criteria: include ecological corridors/migration routes, steppingstone areas, refuges, larval sources and spawning aggregation areas, nursery and breeding grounds and recruitment areas such as larval sinks, as well as developmental and feeding/foraging habitats. The primary strategies for meeting these criteria depend on understanding the distribution and connectivity of species and habitats.
- Understanding the *distribution of species and habitats* is essential in MPAs to identify critical areas important for biodiversity, breeding and feeding. This knowledge guides the establishment and adaptive management of MPAs, ensuring the conservation of marine ecosystems and the resilience of species populations. Modelling the distribution of species and habitats is a highly sophisticated discipline to predict the geographical locations of species and their habitats based on environmental conditions and historical occurrence data. Using statistical techniques and ecological theory, these models can project how species distributions might change in response to various factors, including climate change, habitat alteration and conservation actions. This modelling is crucial for identifying areas of high biodiversity, potential ecological hotspots and regions where conservation efforts are needed. It also helps to understand the impact of environmental change on species migration patterns, and to develop effective strategies for managing and protecting vulnerable species and their habitats. It be analysed from occurrences of adult, juveniles and propagules of a species and habitat mapping, and information can be obtained through dedicated databases as explained in Practice 2, depending on the ecological target.

- *Ecological connectivity* is a prerequisite for the completion of life cycles and the maintenance of species and communities. Conditions that require consideration of connectivity could range from species that occupy isolated habitats and have long pelagic larval durations in deeper marine areas with strong directional currents, to species with short pelagic durations occupying fragmented habitats in shallow, topographically complex marine areas with weak and variable currents. A summary of the principles for incorporating ecological spatial connectivity into the design and management of networks of MPAs established to protect short- and long-distance species and ecological communities and ecosystems is provided in Tables 1 and 2 of D3.2. The main methodological approaches used to measure ecological connectivity are: Lagrangian modelling, animal tagging, genetics (to study gene flow linked to reproduction), simple observation, seascape measures (e.g., habitat connectivity) (for a more detailed description see section 3.2.4.3 D3.2). Data required range from reproductive characteristics of the species, dispersal of eggs, larvae, juveniles and/or adults, recruitment rates and dynamics (indicating whether propagules from neighbouring subpopulations are needed to maintain local populations or whether the subpopulation occupying an area is self-seeding), duration of the larval phase, larval buoyancy, sources and destinations of larvae, home range of adults.
- *Climate-smart potential inner criteria* (concentrative potential of species of climatic interest, potential for mitigation, potential for adaptation, connectivity potential, climatic stability, including dynamic stability and climate-refugia). Selection of criteria and methodological approaches are detailed in D3.3.

Additional general information for scoping can include:

- *Human use* involves a wide range of activities, all of which need to be carefully managed to balance ecological conservation with societal benefits. These activities are scaled and regulated to ensure that they are consistent with conservation objectives and support both the protection of marine biodiversity and the socio-economic well-being of local communities.
- *Human pressures*, pertinent to the examination at hand, encompass a range of anthropogenic activities and their resultant impacts, as detailed in the MSFD and outlined in Annex 1 (D2.2), under Category 3, "Anthropogenic Criteria (Activities and Impacts)". In the scoping phase, human pressures relevant to the research question are identified and defined.
- *Climatic stressors* are selected based on criteria such as the management question, temporal scale, spatial scale, and management target/level. A compilation of climatic drivers is provided in D2.2 (Annex A: 4.1 drivers) and D3.3 (Table 3). The scoping phase will outline the complexity of the analysis in relation to the management question, encompassing both the species in question and their spatial and temporal boundaries. Climatic stressors are associated with climate drivers like sea surface temperature and storminess, whereas non-climatic stressors encompass anthropogenic and abiotic factors. Within the ESE1 framework, these pressures are viewed as cumulative.

Box 1. Application of the Vulnerability Macro-criterion regarding Management question purpose

Example of Management question treatment in Scoping phase

"How to prioritize marine mammals' species to be protected according to climate change in NW Mediterranean for 2030?"

In this example, the geographical and time scale boundaries are well defined, and we know that climate change need to be considered:

- Criterion 1 *Desirable spatio-temporal scale of the analysis* (Highlighting the boundaries) application: Projections need to be "Near Term" and limited to the Med Sea (so the considered **stressor** is mainly Sea Surface Temperature regarding actual data availability and knowledge.)
- Criterion 2 *Type of output* application: the output should be a metric that could be ranked (score or quantitative) as the main purpose of the question is to compare and prioritize species. **Trait-**

based vulnerability assessment is suitable as it will evaluate the influence of climate change on the species and provide a metric for comparison.

- Criterion 3 *Expertise/Complexity of the model* application: Marine mammals are moving species that will probably move before presenting the appearance of adaptations to climate change. Moreover, near-term questions are less likely to induce evolutionary process. For these reasons, a trait-based vulnerability assessment based only on **Sensitivity criteria** is particularly suitable to compare the near-term answers between species and will be selected to feed the macro-criterion **Vulnerability** in the **Analysis and Diagnosis Practices**. The selection of a single criterion among the criteria feeding the Vulnerability macro-criterion will respect the parsimony approach (simple equation) and lead to an acceptable level of uncertainty.
- Final output of the scoping: in this example, the output of the scoping will be to use a **Trait-based vulnerability** assessment based only on **Sensitivity criteria** to sea surface temperature.

Example of promoted approaches issued of the scoping phase considering 4 main management question clusters (questions from test sites)

- **Management question non-ecologically linked (based only on climatic parameters)**

Examples:

“How to identify future conditions in the areas of interest?”

“How to take into account climate change to prioritize space use within a multi-use MPA?”

These questions could be assessed only by considering physical change in climatic conditions. In this way **Anomalies approaches** are sufficient to answer that question and highlight the areas that will be the most influenced by climate change. In this case data selection will be limited to stressors-related data (more details in D3.3, section 3.2.4).

- **Management question including ecological process:** e.g., Management question aiming to evaluate the physiological potential response of a species to climate change.

Examples:

“Does climate change influence the reef-former *Janice conchilega* in the Belgian coastal area?”

“How vulnerable marine ecosystems will adapt to climate change within our MPA?”

For this type of management question, **trait-based Vulnerability approaches** are adapted to evaluate the degree of influence climate change will have on it and individuals' responses. This type of question makes it possible to distinguish the species pool for which climate change needs to be included in the analysis and the inner potential of species to adapt or recover under climate change influence. In this case, traits-data need to be collected.

- **Management question including spatially explicit ecological process:** e.g., Management question aiming to follow a species or an area future trajectory/connectivity

Examples:

“How to predict the future of cod and sprat nurseries in the Bay of Gdansk regarding climate change in MSP?”

“How to identify future areas of interest integrating climate change?”

Here, **trait-based Vulnerability approaches** need to be accompanied by complementary spatial approaches. If the question is related to a given management entities (e.g., existent MPA), Vulnerability analysis could be followed by a comparative analysis of **Vulnerable species' distribution** and projection of future conditions to highlight overlaps. If the question is related to connectivity, **velocities analysis** (especially biotic velocities) for the vulnerable species could be an asset to evaluate spatio-temporal migration trajectories (D3.3, section 3.2.4).

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- **Management question including decision support tool:** e.g., Management question including a prioritization ranking of species/areas influenced by climate change.

Examples:

“How to prioritize areas to be protected according to climate change?”

“How to protect species of priority for conservation in the context of climate change?”

This set of questions is going a step further in the ESE Practices, entering the **Prioritization and Design** Practices and including the need to compare **Vulnerability** outputs to define management scenarios. These questions will mobilize all the data gathered for the previous cluster of questions and will require the use of decision support tools. To ensure a correct comparison to the Vulnerability score between species, we highly recommend the use of a unique **Vulnerability matrix** (e.g., the matrix of trait developed by Butt et al. (2022) as it is the most simple, up-to-date and complete matrix found in the literature) assuming that a value of 0 will be given to the traits when absent for the considered species and 1 when present (See Analysis and diagnosis practices, D3.3 section 3.3.2).

3.3.2 Practice 2 - Data and representation

This practice is based on the results of the previous step/practice (Scoping) and involves gathering and organizing all data related to the previously identified species/habitats, macro-criteria and inner criteria with methodological strategies and all additional information (e.g., human activities, exogenous and endogenous drivers) necessary to support the subsequent phases (e.g., Analysis and Diagnosis, Prioritization) as better specified in the Scoping phase. The objective of this practice is also to harmonize the information and make it easily analysable, as well as represent it in an accessible way.

For the collection of information, it is proposed to follow the approach presented by the MSP Data Framework (MSPdF) (Abramic et al., 2023). The framework, initially developed to support MSP processes, can more generally be considered suitable for supporting different types of area-based design and management processes. These processes require the collection of spatial data and information related to a great variety of issues and themes.

When facing the data collection task, it is necessary to answer questions such as:

- How can we define the marine environment or marine biodiversity?

- What type of data should be collected and included in the analysis for suitability zoning of economic activities, CEA, or land-sea interactions?
- What are the relevant maritime and coastal uses?
- What type of information needs to be collected within the socio-economic and governance topics?

By utilizing the MSPdF, practitioners can address these questions and ensure that the data collection process is comprehensive, systematic, and aligned with the objectives of the MPA design and management. This framework provides guidance on defining relevant spatial data, identifying key issues and processes, and integrating socio-economic and governance considerations into the data collection and analysis process.

The MSPdF emphasizes organizing the collection of information into thematic clusters to facilitate effective data collection and management:

1. Marine & Coastal Environment
2. Marine & Coastal Conservation and Designated sites
3. Oceanographic characteristics and Climate
4. Coastal Land use and Planning
5. Operational maritime activities and Maritime Spatial Planning
6. Socio-economic information
7. Governance information

Within each cluster, the MSPdF also proposes detailed approaches for the classification and categorization of information. For the organization of the Ecological Toolkit we are particularly interested in the development of Cluster 1, Cluster 2, Cluster 3 and Cluster 5.

Below is proposed a detailed breakdown of the information for these thematic clusters which is suggested to be used for the collection and organization of relevant information (see Abramic et al., 2023 and Menegon et al., 2023 for more details).

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Cluster 1 - Marine & Coastal Environment		
<p>Information on coastal and marine environments to evaluate sustainability of the maritime activities. E.g., ecological and ecosystems' characteristics, state of the environment, ecosystems' carrying capacity, pressure of the maritime activities. As outlined in the MSP, environmental cluster data can be classified according to MSFD and/or WFD classifications, where applicable. Beside the hierarchical MSFD classification, an additional attribute can be associated with the data, namely Descriptor and/or Criteria.</p> <p>A non-MSFD classification, not foreseen in the MSPdF, has been added for those data that cannot clearly be associated with the MSFD classification, such as emerged coastal habitats, non-seabirds, seamounts, etc.</p>		
MSFD Classification		
Ecosystems	Species	Marine birds
		Mammals
		Cephalopods
		Reptiles
		Fish
	Habitats	Water column
		Seabed
	Ecosystems, including food webs	Biological characteristics
		Functions and processes
Pressures	Biological	Input or spread of non-indigenous species
		Input of microbial pathogens
		Input of genetically modified species and translocation of native species
		Disturbance of species due to human presence

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		Extraction of, or mortality/injury to, wild species
	Physical	Physical disturbance to seabed
		Physical loss
		Changes to hydrological conditions
	Substances, litter and energy	Input of nutrients - diffuse sources, point sources, atmospheric deposition
		Input of organic matter - diffuse sources and point sources
		Input of other substances - diffuse sources, point sources, atmospheric deposition, acute events
		Input of litter
		Input of anthropogenic sound
		Input of other forms of energy
		Input of water - point sources

Cluster 2 - Marine & Coastal Conservation and Designated sites

Various coastal and marine protection, conservation and designated sites, ranging from the international to the national/local scale. Examples include Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and Fishery Restricted Areas (FRA). Additionally, it incorporates designations related to non-standard conservation, such as potential Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures (OECM), as well as designations for safety, security, and risk control from natural and man-made hazards (e.g., collision risk areas, flooding risk areas). In the context of Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP), this information plays a crucial role in evaluating potential (in)compatibilities of specific current and future uses and activities with marine and coastal protected areas. It is also relevant for assessing (in)compatibilities with various conservation

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<p>figures and designations within maritime sectors managed by MSP. Understanding the conservation objectives associated with each designated area is essential in this regard.</p>	
<p>Conservation types</p>	
<p>Internationally designated Protected Areas (marine and coastal)</p>	
<p>Regionally designated Protected Areas (marine and coastal)</p>	
<p>Nationally designated Protected Areas (marine and coastal)</p>	
<p>Potential Other Effective area-based Conservation Measures (OECMs)</p>	
<p>Recognised areas of protection/conservation value</p>	
<p>Cluster 3 - Oceanographic and Climate Change</p>	
<p>Oceanographic and climatic characteristics, including various physical and chemical parameters such as sea temperature, salinity, atmospheric pressure, bathymetry, winds, currents, waves, oxygen, nutrients, and dissolved organic carbon. These parameters play a crucial role in defining natural potential or constraints for maritime uses and activities, such as offshore wind farms, aquaculture, and wave energy. Monitoring oceanographic conditions is essential for understanding local climate, identifying trends, and assessing the impact of climate change on Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP), influencing both the natural potential and limiting factors within marine sectors.</p>	
<p>Physics</p>	<p>Sea state</p>
	<p>Ocean surface stress</p>
	<p>Bathymetry</p>
	<p>Sea ice</p>
	<p>Sea surface height</p>
	<p>Sea surface temperature</p>
	<p>Subsurface temperature</p>
	<p>Surface currents</p>
	<p>Subsurface currents</p>
	<p>Sea surface salinity</p>
	<p>Subsurface salinity</p>
	<p>Ocean surface heat flux</p>
	<p>Waves</p>
<p>Biochemistry</p>	<p>Oxygen</p>
	<p>Nutrients</p>
	<p>Inorganic carbon</p>

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	Transient tracers	
	Particulate matter	
	Ammonium	
	Nitrate	
	Stable carbon isotopes	
	Chlorophyll-a	
Cluster 5 - Maritime Activities and MSP		
Distribution of maritime activities and MSP designated areas regarding for example fisheries, maritime transport, nautical activities, aquaculture, defence, renewable energy, mineral extraction, and maritime tourism to assess potential conflicts and synergies, and to assess pressure and impact on the environment. This data cluster also includes data such as suitability maps for various activities (e.g., aquaculture and wind farms), providing valuable support for future scenario building and planning purposes.		
iHILUCS Classification System (simplified version) (Abramic et al. 2019)		
Primary production	Aquaculture	Finfish
		Shellfish
	Mining and quarrying	Oil & Gas
		Dredging
		Dumping
	Fishing	Professional fishing
Recreational fishing		
Secondary production	Energy production	Renewable energy
	Other industries	Desalination
Tertiary production	Cultural entertainment and recreational services	Nautical sports
		Beaches
		Coastal tourism
		Underwater cultural heritage

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Transport networks logistics and utilities	Transport	Harbours
		Anchorage area
		Maritime traffic
		Transport trends
	Logistic and storage services	Offshore supply
	Utilities	Electricity gas and thermal power distribution services
		Waste treatment
		Submarine outfall
Submarine cables		
Other uses	Coastal infrastructures	Coastal defence works
	Protected areas	
	Military areas	
	Restricted use	

3.3.2.1 Data collection: examples

In this section, we provide examples of data pertaining to the various clusters, emphasizing their significance in relation to ecological macro-criteria. These examples were extracted from the metadata database compiled by T2.1, which will be maintained as a living document throughout the project’s lifetime and used as a first resource for implementing “Practice 2 - Data and representation” following MSPdF in the process of testing the ESE1 toolkit in the project. This database contains the metadata of over 300 records of datasets, data platforms, tools, and models relevant to MSP4BIO and, more widely, MSP processes in European sea basins. Spatial, temporal, and thematic metadata, considering the desiderata (i.e., guidelines for the collection of potentially

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relevant input data) provided by WP3 and 4, were included in the database. These metadata were used to analyse spatial, temporal, and thematic patterns in the availability of data relevant to MSP4BIO, and the results were presented in D2.1. Each record in the database was classified according to the MSPdF clusters by including a new metadata field, along with the thematic clusters and topics identified in D3.2 and D3.3. MSP4BIO's metadata database is publicly available to browse using the project's data compilation app (<https://msp4bio.vliz.be/>), which can be filtered by MSPdF cluster and other parameters.

Cluster 1 - Marine & Coastal Environment

<u>EMODnet Seabed habitat map (EUSeaMap)</u>	
<p><i>The EMODnet broad-scale seabed habitat map for Europe (EUSeaMap) is a comprehensive, free and ready-to-use broad-scale map of physical habitats, harmonising mapping procedures and fostering a common understanding among seabed mappers in Europe. The map was produced using a "top-down" modelling approach using classified habitat descriptors, including biological zone, energy class, oxygen regime, salinity regime, seabed substrate, and riverine input. The most recent version is EUSeaMap 2023. EMODnet data can be viewed, browsed, subsetting and downloaded using EMODnet's Map Viewer.</i></p>	
Data source	EMODnet
Spatial extent	All European Seas
Resolution or scale	1:250000
Relevance to ecological macro-criteria:	Life cycle critical areas
<u>Marine Species Traits</u>	

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<p>On this data portal, marine taxa can be filtered by functional and structural species traits such as feeding ecology, body size, reproduction, life history, etc. Three main types of traits are documented: biological and ecological traits (e.g., body size or feeding type), taxonomic traits (e.g., paraphyletic groups), and human-defined traits (e.g., Red List species). Taxonomy and environment related information is pulled from the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS), whereas geography data are available through the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS).</p>	<p>Example search: Functional group = benthos, Life stage = adult, Taxon = Abra (genus)</p>
<p>Data source</p>	<p>World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS), Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS), and others.</p>
<p>Spatial extent</p>	<p>Global</p>
<p>Resolution or scale</p>	<p>-</p>
<p>Relevance to ecological macro-criteria:</p>	<p>Vulnerability, stability</p>

Cluster 2 - Marine & Coastal Conservation and Designated sites

<p><u>HELCOM Marine Protected Areas database</u></p> <p>This database contains spatial and descriptive data on all 188 HELCOM MPAs in the Baltic Sea. Data on management plans, species, biotopes, biotope complexes, pressures, and human activities for each MPA can be browsed and downloaded. Further MPA data is available from <u>HELCOM's Map and Data Service</u>.</p>	<p>HELCOM MPAs in the Gdansk Bay area, <u>HELCOM Map and Data Service</u></p>
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Data source	HELCOM
Spatial extent	Baltic Sea
Resolution or scale	-
Relevance to ecological macro-criteria:	Functional hotspots, life cycle critical areas
<u>Conservation status of habitat types and species: datasets from Article 17, Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC reporting</u>	
<p>This dataset contains monitoring and reporting data from EU member states requested by the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC). It includes spatial data on habitat and species distributions and tabular data on habitat areas, population sizes, trends, pressures and threats, and conservation status at the national biogeographical level. Data on conservation status and trends in conservation status at the EU biogeographical level is also included. A web tool allows users to view, browse and visualise the data. A similar dataset related to the Birds Directive (2009/147/EC) is also available.</p>	<p>Spatial visualisation of the conservation status of habitat 1150 (coastal lagoons) from the web tool</p>
Data source	European Environment Agency
Spatial extent	European Union
Resolution or scale	10km
Relevance to ecological macro-criteria:	Vulnerability, functional hotspots, life cycle critical areas

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Cluster 3 – Oceanographic and Climate Change

<p><u>Bio-ORACLE</u></p>	
<p><i>Bio-ORACLE provides 19 physical, chemical, and biological marine data layers, and 7 topographic marine data layers, with global coverage and a temporal resolution of 10 decadal steps, from 2000 to 2100. The essential physical, chemical and biological variables are presented as 6 statistics for surface and benthic conditions, under present-day conditions and the SSP1-1.9, SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP3-7.0, SSP4-6.0 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios.</i></p>	<p>Sea surface temperature in the decade 2070-2080 under SSP3 plotted in R</p>
Data source	Assis et al., 2024; Tyberghein et al., 2012
Spatial extent	Global
Resolution or scale	0.05°
Relevance to ecological macro-criteria:	Stability, potential climate-smart areas
<p><u>Black Sea, Bio-Geo-Chemical, L4, monthly means, daily gapfree and climatology Satellite Observations (Near Real Time)</u></p>	
<p><i>One example of the many physical and (bio)geochemical datasets available from Copernicus Marine Service, this product provides multi-year bio-geochemical regional datasets on phytoplankton chlorophyll concentration and interpolated gap-free chlorophyll concentration. Data is available from September 1997 to the present day at daily and monthly intervals. It can be visualised, subsetting, and downloaded through the MyOcean Pro viewer, along with other Copernicus marine data products.</i></p>	<p>Visualisation of the dataset in MyOcean Pro</p>
Data source	Copernicus Marine Service
Spatial extent	Black Sea (similar datasets are available for other European sea basins and globally)
Resolution or scale	1km / 300m
Relevance to ecological macro-criteria:	Vulnerability, functional hotspots, life cycle critical areas

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Cluster 5 – Maritime Activities and MSP

<u>EMODnet Human Activities, EMSA Route Density Map</u>	
<p>This dataset contains shipping route density maps created using AIS data. These maps are available per ship type (passenger, cargo, tanker, fishing, and all other) and as annual, monthly, or seasonal totals. EMODnet data can be viewed, browsed, subsetting and downloaded using EMODnet's Map Viewer. A similar dataset on vessel density is also available from EMODnet.</p>	<p><i>Route density (annual total of all vessels) in the Azores, from EMODnet's Map Viewer</i></p>
<p>+ Data source</p>	<p>European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA) for EMODnet</p>
<p>Spatial extent</p>	<p>All European seas</p>
<p>Resolution or scale</p>	<p>1km</p>
<p>Relevance to ecological macro-criteria:</p>	<p>Vulnerability</p>
<u>Global Fishing Watch Fishing Effort</u>	
<p>This dataset contains the Global Fishing Watch AIS-based fishing effort and vessel presence datasets. Data are available as fishing effort by flag state and gear type at 100th degree resolution, or fishing effort by MMSI at 10th degree resolution. Each version of the fishing effort dataset is accompanied by a table of vessel information (e.g., gear type, flag state, dimensions, etc.). The data can also be visualised on the map tool. https://globalfishingwatch.org/map</p>	<p><i>Apparent fishing effort in the southern North Sea, 18/02/24 - 18/03/24</i></p>
<p>Data source</p>	<p>Global Fishing Watch, Inc., www.globalfishingwatch.org</p>
<p>Spatial extent</p>	<p>Global</p>
<p>Resolution or scale</p>	<p>0.01° / 0.1°</p>

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Relevance to ecological macrocriteria:

<i>Vulnerability</i>

3.3.2.2 Data management and representation

Here are some methodological and technical elements intended for the "Data and representation" practice. These elements aim to ensure that information is easily usable during the analysis phase and accessible to stakeholders. By making the process replicable and transparent, we can potentially encourage a collaborative approach among stakeholders.

Data storage and organization

- Establish a centralized repository for MPA data, accessible to relevant stakeholders.
- Utilize standardized data formats and metadata schemas to ensure interoperability.
- Implement data versioning and backup mechanisms to safeguard against loss or corruption.
- Organize data according to the MSPdF.

Data sharing and access

- Promote open data policies to maximize accessibility and transparency.
- Develop data sharing agreements to clarify ownership, usage rights, and citation requirements.
- Utilize Spatial Data Infrastructures (SDIs) at international, EU, national, and local levels to facilitate data sharing and interoperability.
- Provide tools and platforms for stakeholders to search, access, and download MPA data.

Data visualization and communication

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- Develop interactive maps, dashboards, and reports to communicate MPA data to diverse audiences.
- Utilize geospatial visualization techniques (e.g., heatmaps, choropleth maps) to highlight patterns and trends.
- Incorporate storytelling elements to engage stakeholders and foster stewardship of marine resources.
- Ensure accessibility of visualizations for users with diverse technical backgrounds and abilities.

Capacity building and training

- Provide training and capacity-building workshops on data management best practices and tools.
- Foster partnerships with academic institutions, NGOs, and government agencies to support skills development.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and peer-to-peer learning within the MPA management community.

Continuous Improvement and Adaptation

- Establish mechanisms for feedback and evaluation to identify areas for improvement.
- Regularly update data management protocols to incorporate advancements in technology and methodologies.

Adapt data management strategies in response to changing environmental conditions, stakeholder needs, and regulatory requirements.

3.3.3 Practice 3 - Analysis and diagnosis

Aim of the practice. This practice supports the diagnosis of the current state of the marine environment and understanding the key ecological processes at play. The diagnosis includes understanding the cause-effect relationships, starting from pressures (deriving from human activities and climate change), determining the state (of marine ecosystems and biodiversity) and eventually impacts (already in place or possible, at present and/or in the future). To clarify and possibly quantify such cause-effect nexus, macro-criteria should be assessed here (by using their respective indicators), and specific DSTs can be applied.

In this section, we present a comprehensive list of metrics and strategic methodologies corresponding to ecological macro-criteria and inner criteria.

3.3.3.1 Vulnerability inner criteria

Inner vulnerability criteria include sensitivity, resistance, resilience/recovery and adaptivity, and related analysis methods depend on the framework of the management questions. In the Analysis and Diagnosis step of the ESE, vulnerability such as its intrinsic criteria (e.g., sensitivity) will not be used as a criterion by itself but as a metric, the vulnerability score, binding abiotic (climatic condition) to biotic components (species traits). The vulnerability score will be used to analyse cause-effect relationships, especially understanding and quantifying the effects of climate change on the management target. The vulnerability macro-criterion is the first to be mobilized in this ESE phase to the dataset as it englobes all the methods leading to: 1) the calculation of the metric on which the next stage of the ESE will be based, 2) the proposition of an initial assessment of the results by highlighting the areas concentrating the stakes (e.g., hotspot of vulnerable species, areas heavily influenced by climate change) and indicate potential management target, 3) the support and guidance of the step-by-step definition of spatio-

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temporal sequences of climatic condition evolution (climate-analog velocities) in a defined area leading to the identification of potential future ecological corridors. In that respect, the vulnerability macro-criterion will feed the connectivity criteria and the climate-smart potential and stability macro-criteria and mobilized most of the climate change-related tools. In BOX2, we report examples of Analysis and Diagnosis application of vulnerability calculation methodologies chosen in Scoping practices based on vulnerability macro-criterion to calculate the vulnerability score coming from the three first clusters of questions defined in BOX1.

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Box 2. Example of application of Vulnerability macro-criterion and climate change-related Methods in the Analysis and Diagnosis ESE practices framing (synthesis of key concept from D3.3)

Cluster 1. Management questions non-ecologically linked

For questions from cluster 1, the purpose of the Analysis and Diagnosis Practices is to compare a current chosen climatic value (such as temperature) to a series of reference called *Climate Normal* to detect anomalies (intensity and frequency). The number and the intensity of anomalies detected by these comparisons will provide a proxy of the importance of climate change incidence on the different areas of interest. More information about this approach could be found in D3.3, section 3.2.4.

Cluster 2. Management question including ecological process

This second cluster of questions is the most complicated to evaluate as it needs to be supported by a clear analysis of management question during the scoping phase and rationale to select the most appropriate way to calculate Vulnerability score. The most appropriate way to calculate Vulnerability score refers both to the acceptable level of uncertainty defined in the analysis framework (D3.3, section 4.3) and the management target.

Analysis method 1. Sensitivity-based Vulnerability analysis

Example: “Does climate change influence the reef-former *Lanice conchilega* in the Belgian coastal area?”

Sensitivity-based Vulnerability analysis mobilize only the Sensitivity criteria. The calculation of the vulnerability score is based on the sum of sensitivity traits presented by the specie of interest. Higher is the vulnerability score, higher is the sensitivity of the species to the chosen climatic stressor(s). The difficulty is to set a relevant threshold/benchmark for species for which literature is scarce (D3.3, section 4.2).

Equation of sensitivity-based vulnerability analysis for a single stressor (from Butt et al., 2022):

$$\text{Sensitivity score } S_{ij} = \sum_k S_{jk}$$

With s_{ij} = sensitivity of a species i to the given stressor j , et s_{jk} the sensitivity to the stressor j of the trait k . The additive method is promoted for the ESE regarding the actual knowledge available in the different test sites to decrease the level of uncertainty concerning the interaction between the stressors. It is nevertheless advised to tend towards more comprehensive analysis integrating climate stressors interaction in the future.

In that example a matrix of traits could be found in the Biological Traits Information Catalogue (BIOTIC) (Marine Life Information Network. Plymouth: Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom, 2006). Sensitivity values need to be attributed per trait. The overall characteristic of the species defining it as low sensitive to rising temperatures.

Analysis method 2. Integrative Vulnerability analysis

Example: “How Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems will adapt to climate change within our MPA?”

The influence of climate change on a management target will, in reality, depend on two components: its sensitivity to given climatic stressor(s) and its potential physiological and physical response to climate change. In that case, Resistance, Resilience/Recovery and Adaptation criteria will be mobilized. The

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temporal-scale of the management target will define the criteria to consider. Traits for Resistance and Resilience/Recovery (near-term response) will be included in the sensitivity matrix and associated with a Low Level of Sensitivity. The rationale is that the possession of a trait of resilience and resistance will decrease the level of overall Sensitivity of the species by conferring advantages. As Sensitivity score is dependent of the number of traits of each category considered, we highly recommend to be assisted by an expert for the design of the standardized Sensitivity matrix integrative of main species traits (see Butt et al., 2022). This integrative matrix must be duplicated and filled for each climatic stressor(s) considered. Moreover, the Adaptive criterion must be mobilized for long-term projection. Adaptive Capacity is generally highly uncertain and mainly linked to plasticity, genetic and reproductive traits. This criterion will be particularly suitable for levels of analysis higher than species level (e.g., community, habitats, ecosystem, areas) and non-moving species such as *Lanice conchigula* from the previous example. In this case, the Vulnerability equation (Cannizzo et al., 2023) will be modified as follow:

$$\text{Vulnerability} = (\text{Exposure} + \text{Sensitivity}) - \text{Adaptive Capacity}$$

For example, regarding the example of Box 1. “How to prioritize marine mammals’ species to be protected according to climate change in NW Mediterranean for 2030?”

The species is a moving species, with a near-term objective, the Adaptive criterion does not appear relevant to be mobilized. The **method 1. Sensitivity-based Vulnerability analysis** appears sufficient. In this example from Chatzimentor et al., 2022, the **Sensitivity score** highlight that, from a conservative point of view, the monk seal *Monachus monachus* and the Sperm whales *Physeter macrocephalus* are the most sensitive to climate change. This indicates a more urgent need to consider climate change in the planning of the management measure and MPA design for these species compared with the list of marine mammal’s species defined in **Scoping** phase.

Interspecific sensitivity traits matrix

Species' names	Specialized requirements on habitat	Vertical migration ability	Use of habitats likely to be impacted by SLR*	Specialized requirements on diet	Preference in narrow thermal conditions	Dispersability	Impact score of other non-climatic threats	IUCN status	Generation length	Body size	Sensitivity scores (quantitative or qualitative)
Balaenoptera physalus	low	high	moderate	low	high	low	low	low	high	high	moderate
Delphinus delphis	low	high	low	high	high	low	low	moderate	moderate	high	moderate
Monachus monachus	moderate	high	moderate	low	high	moderate	low	high	moderate	high	high
Physeter macrocephalus	moderate	high	moderate	high	high	low	low	moderate	low	high	high
Stenella coeruleoalba	low	high	low	low	high	low	low	low	high	high	moderate

Cluster 3. Management question including spatially explicit ecological process

Applied to examples from Box 1.

“How to predict the future of cod and sprat nurseries in the Bay of Gdansk regarding climate change in MSP?”

“How to identify future areas of interest integrating climate change?”

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For questions from cluster 3, the Vulnerability macro-criterion will be based on 3 key elements: the Vulnerability of Species of interest, Species of interest distribution and spatialized future climatic conditions (See figure below). Vulnerability/Sensitivity score provides a ranking of species according to their response to climate change, sum of current species distribution highlights the hotspot of vulnerable and resistant species while its superposition to future climatic conditions enables the localization and the quantification of the loss of species range. Finally, combination of species desirability traits (e.g., movement capacity, adaptivity, see D3.3 section 3.3) and velocities (both analog-based and biotic) provides potential future ecological corridors and first proposition of connectivity design among areas that still need to be categorized using the other macro-criteria.

Crossing exposure and sensitivity using *Species Distribution*

Vulnerability Assessment in progress, the methodologies will be further discussed in the guidance

Theoretical example of complete application on the Bottlenose dolphin (*T. truncatus*) to answer to the management question “How to predict the future of Bottlenose dolphin in the Mediterranean Sea regarding climate change in MSP?” using climate change-related tools and criteria. As previously indicated, Sensitivity score indicates that *T. truncatus* is moderately threatened by climate change in Mediterranean Sea as it presents high mobility capacities (and related traits, that decrease its Sensitivity score). Using this information and using SST as proxy for climate change exposure, we will try to answer to the management question combining climate forward velocities (a., future condition projection), current species distribution (b) and known movement pattern of the species. In this theoretical (not proved by example, two sites in green appear as potential **Stable** areas (climate-refugia) for the species.

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3.3.3.2 Stability inner criteria

The stability inner criteria (redundancy, ecosystem integrity and adaptivity) can be analysed through functional diversity, vulnerability assessment and ecological connectivity, as these are essential prerequisite to maintain stability, persistence and adaptation (paragraph 3.2.4 in D3.2). Different approaches and metrics are detailed in D3.2 and D3.3 (see Box 2). Here we briefly present some potential methodological approaches (for references see D3.2 and D3.3) mainly through calculating species composition indexes (richness, evenness, etc.) and proxies of functional diversity obtained using species traits. Using metrics based on biological traits offers an alternative perspective through the traditional application of species richness, evenness or other diversity matrices based on counts or proportions, making the trait-based approach more applicable to a wide variety of spatial scales. In some cases, easily measurable

morphological traits can serve as cost-effective and time-efficient proxies. Distribution of species is obtained by detecting functional group on the base on traits and their abundances) in the functional space of a given community. A functional space is a multidimensional space where the axes are functional traits along which species are placed according to their functional trait values.

- *Functional richness indices* are proxies of functional diversity provide a measure of functional hotspots and stability and are based on species occurrences and species traits, a list of indices can be found in D3.2. The fundiversity R package is provides efficient, modular, and parallel functions to compute six functional diversity indices: functional divergence (FDiv), function evenness (FEve), FRic, FRic intersections (FRic_intersect), functional dispersion (FDis), and Rao's entropy (Q) (reviewed in Villéger et al. 2008). Functional diversity indices are based on species traits data, i.e., species characteristics. A complete guideline can be found at <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/fundiversity/fundiversity.pdf>. Among these indices, the FRic index is the most used. FRic is computed as the volume of the convex hull from all included traits (Villéger et al. 2008).
- *Combining functional redundancy & functional dispersion index*. Functional redundancy, as proxies of insurance (i.e., when one species is able to replace a similar species from the same functional niche) can be measured by binning multiple species traits with the Sturges algorithm (i.e., data were divided into classes based on the sample size and distribution of values across each trait). Functional dispersion, (i.e., breadth of roles across taxa) is an indicator of response diversity and can be generated by computing pairwise dissimilarities of transformed traits using the Gower dissimilarity matrix. Then in order to identify regions with unique patterns of redundancy and dispersion, it is necessary to

compare these measures from the null expectation, given their species richness in a particular ecoregion.

- *Combining compositional & functional β -diversity components.* Nestedness and turnover define diverse ecological processes driving biodiversity patterns. Nestedness relates to variations in the number of species (or functional traits, or any other type of features used to quantify diversity) due to gain or loss, so that the pools of species in less diverse assemblages appear nested as a strict subset of the more diverse ones. Turnover occurs when species loss is balanced by the arrival of new ones. As pointed in D3.2, Bevilacqua and Terlizzi (2020) through an example offer a conceptual framework to select, prioritize sites/habitats for protection by combining information on compositional and functional β -diversity components. They analyse species composition (number and type of species present in a habitat) and species functional traits (see Figure 5 in D3.2).

3.3.3.3 Functional hotspots inner criteria

Inner criteria for functional hotspots are presence of key functional species such as apex predators, primary producers, or other specific trophic group, functionally rare species, key function areas, i.e., areas presenting critical/key functions. Strategy for addressing functional hotspots is mainly based on functional diversity and trophic ecology approaches and metrics.

- *Biological traits analysis (BTA) as proxy to describe ecological functioning.* This approach uses a number of biological characteristics expressed by the taxa present as indicators of key ecosystem functions. Biological traits can help to define the area boundaries which display higher value of a target function. In this case species having defined functional traits are plotted over a geographic space. Frid et al. (2008), tested the traits approach feasibility on the definition of MPA boundaries through identification of organisms' functional roles and crucial

ecosystem functions using a centred (covariance) Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and co-inertia analyses. The PCA allows the scoring of differences of ecological structures among benthic communities and graphically presenting the range of ecological characteristics of these communities (e.g., range of the type of sea bottom). The co-inertia analysis was used to examine the differences of ecological functioning among the sampled stations in the study and similarly to PCA, scores these differences. However, the co-inertia analysis combines two types of data: the abundance of taxa from each study location and their biological traits.

- *Trophic ecology approach.* Understanding the structural properties of food webs may help to identify key species (predators, preys), primary producers, etc., although this requires large amounts of data that are not always available. A selection of operational food-web indicators for the assessment in marine waters are reported by Tam et al. (2017). These include the primary production required to sustain a fishery, the productivity of seabirds (or charismatic megafauna), zooplankton indicators, primary productivity, integrated trophic indicators and the biomass of trophic guilds. Dietary composition indicates prey importance. This can be assessed through the quantification of the frequency of prey occurrence in predators' stomach, via visual inspection or eDNA trace. Animal stomach content has been used to contribute to the definition of EBSAs (refer to section 3.2.3.3 in D3.2).

Assessing functions (e.g., primary and secondary production rates, Carbon storage potential) is a strategy to spot and define areas of high functional value. Community data such as diversity, species composition, abundance, biomass, and distribution also provide other relevant information. Individual properties such as size are also relevant. Size is an important parameter and may be used to extrapolate metrics such as secondary production, from individuals to community level.

3.3.3.4 Life cycle critical areas inner criteria

Inner criteria include ecological corridors/migration pathways, steppingstone areas, refuge areas, sources of larvae and spawning aggregations areas, nursery and breeding grounds, recruitment areas (larval sinks), developmental and feeding/foraging habitats/areas. A possible methodological strategy to address these inner criteria is based on species and habitat distribution and ecological connectivity.

- *Species/habitat distribution* can be assessed by mapping species/habitat occurrences and defining dispersion in space. This defines the geographic limits of a particular taxon's distribution, i.e., its home range. Critical habitats for life cycles are defined based on the best ecological knowledge on the species biology related to particular traits (reproductive mode, feeding mode, movement capacity etc.).
- *Ecological connectivity* is measured through passive and active movements of propagules, larvae and adults, a prerequisite for completing species life cycles among critical habitats. The main methodological approaches to measure ecological connectivity are observation (visual census, video recording) and eDNA tracking of the presence of a specie or propagules (e.g., spotting steppingstone areas), tracking movements (through telemetry tagging methods) or individual-based modelling, connectivity matrices (i.e., source distribution matrix) (for a detailed description refer to section 3.2.4.3 in D3.2). Modelling approaches on single species to define dispersal trajectories, connectivity matrices and dispersal kernels are commonly used. Metrics should be tailored for taxa with different spawning and larval traits (larval phase duration, larval buoyancy, etc.). In dispersal simulations, based on the best ecological knowledge, it should be possible to assume if propagules either drift passively with currents or have simple behaviour (e.g., sinking, diel vertical migration). Another parameter to consider in

the case of planktonic propagule is the larval phase duration, since it is a proxy of dispersal distances, which can last from a few hours to hundreds of days. Dispersal simulations need a reliable representation of both the magnitude and direction of marine currents transporting larvae based on hydrodynamic simulations, possibly validated against available observations and at a spatial resolution that is sufficient to resolve the dynamics important for connectivity (such as coastal dynamics, eddies, i.e., in the order of a few hundreds of meters). High-variability of currents should also be considered at spatio-temporal scales relevant for both dispersal processes (larval scale) and regional connectivity estimates (population scale, including demographic variability). Another variable to consider is the horizontal resolution which might influence simulated connectivity patterns. Examples of structural connectivity metrics that reflect the physical arrangement of habitats are the distance to nearest neighbor patch (data: patch boundaries, distance between focal patches), the distance to nearest occupied patch (data: patch boundaries, distance between focal patches, occupancy status of patch), the degree of connectedness, fraction of nodes connected to a focal node. A detailed description of metrics is provided by Keeley et al. (2021). For tools integrating connectivity refer to section 4 of this deliverable and the extensive overview provided in D3.2.

3.3.3.5 Climate-smart potential inner criteria

This macro-criterion involves the output of previously presented macro-criteria as it is the most comprehensive but uncertain criteria. Its inner criteria (concentrative potential of species of climatic interest, potential for mitigation, potential for adaptation, connectivity potential and climatic stability) can be analysed using the combination of methods for other macro-criteria described in the Analysis and Diagnosis phase. Here we briefly complement methodological approaches by focussing on potential for mitigation, which was not yet included in the ESE1. Regarding actual knowledge, potential for mitigation is

today mainly linked to Carbon sequestration and acidity buffering and depends on projected functional diversity, trophic and ecosystem regulation processes. Indicator species (e.g., teleost fish) and habitats (e.g., sandy floor) abundance could be used to identify potential mitigation areas (D3.3, section 5.1.2.2.6 and 5.2.2.3). The connectivity potential could be evaluated by analysing biotic velocities (D3.3, section 5.1.2.2.3).

A very versatile metric for geospatially incorporating climate change drivers is analog-based velocity. The climate change analog-based velocity (D3.3, section 3.2.4) is a metric of distance (spatial, temporal or spatio-temporal) between the climatic conditions in an area of interest and the nearest area presenting similar climate conditions (Carroll et al., 2015). Two different types of velocities could be defined when time is considered: the backward velocity to identify similar areas to those of interest in the past (to optimize the benefits of feedback between MPAs with similar climatic trajectories) and the forward velocity to identify similar areas in the future (to define potential migration pathways and assist range shift). Calculating analog-based velocities involves developing current and projected future climate conditions maps.

3.3.4 Practice 4 - Prioritization and designation

Based on the scoping, data management and analysis practices, priorities are set for conservation and management actions within the MPA. This step involves determining which areas or habitats are most critical for protection and designating them as part of the MPA.

A step-by-step methodology for prioritization and designation of MPAs includes:

- *Defining priority sets.* Utilize stakeholder input, expert knowledge, and ecological criteria to establish priority sets for conservation and management actions within the MPA. This involves identifying which areas or habitats are most critical for protection based on conservation goals and ecological significance.

- *Applying conservation algorithms.* Utilize conservation planning software which employ mathematical algorithms to identify priority areas for conservation (see section 4 in this deliverable). These tools optimize the selection of protected areas to maximize biodiversity representation and connectivity while considering spatial constraints and conservation targets. Such algorithms rely on spatial data layers representing biodiversity features, habitat suitability, ecological processes, and conservation constraints. Additionally, socio-economic data layers, such as economic value, land tenure, and cultural significance, can be incorporated to guide decision-making and prioritize conservation actions that balance ecological and socio-economic objectives.
- *Analysing results.* Evaluate the outputs generated by the conservation algorithms to identify potential Marine Protected Area configurations that best meet conservation goals and priority sets. Assess the spatial distribution of selected areas and their ecological significance in relation to the broader marine landscape.
- *Stakeholder engagement.* Engage stakeholders, including local communities, scientists, government agencies, and non-governmental organizations, throughout the prioritization process. Seek feedback on proposed MPA designs, address concerns, and ensure transparency in decision-making.
- *Iterative refinement.* Refine the prioritization analysis iteratively based on stakeholder feedback, new data availability, and changing conservation objectives. Continuously update and improve MPA designations to adapt to evolving ecological conditions and management needs.

4. Decision support tools and their development for ESE1

4.1 Overview and desktop assessment of spatially explicit decision support tools

Seven DSTs created and implemented across Europe with promising capabilities to contribute to the design and management of area-based protection measures were identified. The data incorporated and the geographic scope of the outputs produced would allow these tools to support planning and decision-making actions with different aims in all major European sea basins. However, given the nature of the data available and the features offered, none of the identified tools alone could cover all ecological and environmental dimensions of relevance highlighted in D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3 for the process of designing and managing MPAs (Table 4.1). Therefore, without an ideal tool covering all the needs of MPA processes in a given sea basin, the best approach would be to combine different DSTs to inform decision-making processes effectively.

Tools including the needed data (or providing the possibility to upload proprietary data) and covering relevant topics are not equally available across European sea basins. Currently, the vast majority of available tools concentrate on the Baltic Sea, with five (PlanWise4Blue, MSP Challenge 2050, Baltic Sea Impact Index, Symphony, Mytilus) out of the seven tools being designed for and effectively implemented only in this sea basin. However, promising tools are also available for the North Sea (MSP Challenge 2050) and the Mediterranean Sea (Tools4MSP; this tool also includes data and applications focusing on the Black Sea), which in combination with those developed in the Baltic Sea can effectively cover most dimensions of relevance in the process of designing and managing MPAs.

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All identified tools provide some kind of applications that produce spatially explicit outputs that can be used in the process of informing the identification and prioritizing EBSAs and provide relevant modules for the development of environmental impact assessments. Existing applications in different tools for performing CEA strongly differ in the type of implemented algorithms and data used (see section 4.2.2 for further details and examples on available applications performing CEA). Only a few tools (PlanWise4Blue and Zonation 5) incorporate explicit applications for the assessment and prioritization of alternative conservation strategies considering ecological, environmental and human pressures information in combination with implementation costs (see further details of a recent developments of PlanWise4Blue in section 4.2.4).

Tools incorporating connectivity through the explicit consideration of dispersion (active and passive) and migration processes (functional connectivity) and seascape features that facilitate or prevent the movement of organisms (structural connectivity) are still rare. Currently, Zonation 5 and PlanWise4Blue (the latter through recent developments incorporated in the frame of MSP4BIO, see section 4.2.4) are able to consider connectivity in their prioritization algorithms. This is mainly done through the consideration of structural aspects of habitats that facilitate the movement of species (habitat cohesion and integrity, corridors) when prioritizing different conservation strategies. Functional connectivity, i.e., the actual movement of organisms, has not been explicitly and effectively incorporated in the assessed tools. The difficulties to generate reliable data (thing that has been changing in the last decade with the improvement of tracking technologies and methods for the analysis of genetic and chemical markers) and the computational demands of algorithms used to model different connectivity processes have prevented the effective consideration of functional connectivity in decision-making processes. However, a recent academic exercise using Symphony has shown how to incorporate information on larval dispersion derived from a Lagrangian particle-tracking model in a CEA (Jonsson et al., 2021).

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Different tools have already or are in the process of incorporating applications for analyzing the effects of climate change on relevant nature values. A promising development in the frame of the MSP4BIO is a prototype for using analog-based climate velocity for climate adaptation planning within the Tools4MSP platform (see an in-detail explanation of this application's functionalities in section 4.2.3.2). This application provides a practical implementation of the key concepts introduced in D3.3.

The information available on official webpages and associated documents indicates that most tools have not been incorporated in the design, implementation and management of MPAs across Europe. Zonation 5 has been implemented in academic exercises evaluating how effective established MPAs are in protecting biodiversity hotspots and the need for expanding the area protected by the currently established network of MPAs in Finland (Virtanen et al., 2018). Beyond not being formally implemented in actual MPA processes, the revised tools and platforms have well-developed or upcoming applications that, when used in combination, can effectively inform decision-making processes on the design and management of area-based protection measures. Only the consideration of functional connectivity is a pending dimension that should be properly addressed and incorporated in the set of existing DSTs.

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Table 4.1. Overview of decision support tools (DSTs) developed and used in Europe and of their potential to assist the design and management of area-based conservation measures. Essential details such as the name of the tool, its developer and the type of institution responsible for its creation are presented. The overview covers the tool's capabilities in several key areas: 1) identifying and prioritizing ecologically or biologically significant areas (EBSAs), 2) considering connectivity processes, 3) conducting cumulative impact assessments, and 4) assessing the impact of climate change drivers. It also provides information on the types and locations of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) that the tools can potentially address, as specified in the tool's documentation. This information is also derived from studies where DSTs have been used alongside other methods to achieve the stated objectives.

Name	Developer	Institution type	Geographic scope	Users	Application type	Identify EBSAs	Connectivity processes	Cumulative Impacts	Effects of climate change	Type of protected area	Location of protected areas
PW4B	Estonian Marine Institute, University of Tartu	Academic	Baltic Sea	decision makers; NGOs; planning authorities	Web-based	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	not specified	Coastal areas, continental shelves
MSP Challenge 2050	Breda University of Applied Sciences	Academic	North Sea, Baltic Sea	academia; decision makers; NGOs; planning authorities	Desktop; web-based	Yes	No	Yes	No	not specified	Coastal areas, continental shelves
Spatial Pressure and Impact Assessment (SPIA)	Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (HELCOM)	Intergovernmental	Baltic Sea	decision makers; NGOs; planning authorities; private sector; research	Desktop	Yes	No	Yes	No	not specified	Coastal areas, continental shelves
Symphony	Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management (SwAM)	Governmental	Baltic Sea	decision makers; planning authorities	Restricted availability	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	not specified	Coastal areas, continental shelves
Tools4MSP	The National Research Council Institute of Marine Science (CNR-ISMAR)	Academic	Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea	academia; decision makers; planning authorities; students	Web-based	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	not specified	Coastal areas, continental shelves
Mytilus	Aalborg University, Institute of Planning Ocean & Coastal Management	Academic	Baltic Sea	academia; NGOs; planning authorities	Desktop	Yes	No	Yes	No	not specified	Coastal areas, continental shelves
Zonation 5	University of Helsinki	Academic	Global	not specified	Desktop	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	not specified	Coastal area, continental shelves, deep-sea regions

4.2 Upgraded ecological and science-based operational models and tools

4.2.1 Dispersion and connectivity modelling tools

The Pressure assessment of MARine activities (PMAR) module is both a stand-alone tool and an operational integration to the Tools4MSP CEA framework. The CEA module relies on pressure-specific models, which may not always be available or comprehensive. To overcome this challenge, the PMAR approach uses Lagrangian particle tracking algorithms to produce intermediate-quality models that simulate the spread of certain anthropogenic pressures. This enhancement expands the versatility of the CEA tool, allowing for the consideration of a wider range of use, pressure, and receptor combinations. Furthermore, it introduces an innovative approach for exploring potential future scenarios.

PMAR requires two types of input: oceanographic and atmospheric data to drive particle dispersal and trajectory calculations using OpenDrift (as described by Dagestad et al., 2018), and georeferenced layers of human activities, which act as the origins of pressure propagation. Oceanographic and atmospheric data can be directly streamed from well-known open-source European data infrastructures, including the Copernicus Marine Data Store.

PMAR generates georeferenced layers that illustrate the spread of pressures from specified human activities within the area of interest. These layers can be directly analysed to study the pressures or integrated into the CEA module for a comprehensive evaluation of cumulative effects.

PMAR standardises input layers by defining the area of interest and implementing a uniform grid system. It enables customisation of the pressure model by adjusting

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parameters that define the physical properties of the virtual particles, such as buoyancy or decay rate. To reduce the impact of seasonal or annual variations in ocean currents or wind patterns, it combines results from multiple simulations conducted over various time frames. PMAR is a tool designed to assist with marine management and decision-making processes, specifically tailored to MSP. It includes features such as trajectory aggregation methods (allowing the output layer to display either average or maximum trajectory concentrations within the area), the ability to prioritize different human activity layers through weighting, and the option to focus on a specific subsection of the spatial domain. The software's enhanced capabilities also include a vertical dimension for conducting 3D simulations. This allows for the examination of phenomena such as particle sinking, sedimentation, and distribution within the water column. Additionally, the tool enables the addition of various particle types, including oil from spills. It also provides the functionality to filter particles based on their 'status', whether they are in active transport or have ceased movement due to beaching or sinking.

PMAR is fully integrated and operational on the Tools4MSP Geoplatform. Users can create a PMAR case study, select a specific domain region, upload necessary human activity layers, adjust particle characteristics, and initiate the simulation. The generated output can be downloaded as a geotiff file, incorporated into the Geoplatform's layer database, or added to a map interface for dynamic exploration and analysis.

4.2.2 Cumulative effects assessment tools

4.2.2.1 Tools4MSP

The Tools4MSP Geoplatform is a system built on the GeoNode open-source software, which helps people work together on managing location-based information. It has various features that make handling geospatial data easier:

- **Geospatial Data Curation:** Users can easily organize and manage geospatial data, like maps and location-based files. The system supports different data formats such as shapefiles, GeoTIFFs, and KML files.
- **Data Discovery and Metadata Management:** Users can easily find relevant geospatial data using keywords, categories, or spatial information. It also allows users to add detailed information about their datasets, like descriptions, tags, licensing, and data quality.
- **Visualization and Mapping:** The system has tools for creating interactive maps. Users can overlay multiple layers, customize the map's look, apply symbols, and show information about features. It even supports showing data in different coordinate systems.
- **Collaborative Data Sharing:** Users can share their geospatial data with others. The system lets administrators control who can access the data, and users can share data publicly or with specific individuals or groups.
- **Interoperability:** The system allows publishing geospatial data as web services, making it accessible to other applications and users. For example, it can generate Web Map Service (WMS) and Web Feature Service (WFS) endpoints, making it easy for other software to use the data.
- **Data Visualization Widgets:** GeoNode has built-in tools like charts and sliders that make it easier to explore and analyse geospatial data. These tools help tell stories with data and communicate insights effectively.

Beyond its fundamental features, the Geoplatform also incorporates the Tools4MSP modelling framework. This framework is an extensive and unified approach crafted to assist in MSP processes. Tailored for decision-makers, planners, and stakeholders engaged in marine environment management, it provides an organized structure and a set of tools. Developed by CNR-ISMAR since 2013, with collaboration from various

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research institutions, it integrates data, spatial analysis, modelling techniques, and human-computer interaction methodologies. The objective is to streamline informed decision-making and promote sustainable development in coastal and marine areas.

Within the Tools4MSP framework, a specialized module addresses a spatially explicit CEA. Originating from the methodology by Halpern et al. (2008) and subsequently refined by Andersen et al. (2015), Tools4MSP CEA aims to spatially evaluate the impact of individual or multiple human activities on environmental components. It achieves this by explicitly identifying relationships among the source of pressure, pathways of exposure, and the environmental receptors that may be affected. This structured approach, known as source-pressure-pathway-receptor linkages or an impact chain, aligns with key aspects of environmental risk assessment methodologies (Judd et al., 2015; Stelzenmüller et al., 2018).

It is essential to emphasize the importance of understanding the sensitivities of various nature values to different types of pressures when conducting any CEA exercise. However, a major challenge in most analyses is the lack of comprehensive knowledge in this area. Currently, the Tools4MSP tool heavily relies on expert judgment to quantify these effects. Moreover, the Halpern et al. (2008) approach does not account for the quantification of interactive effects among pressures, as it evaluates the impact of each pressure in isolation before aggregating the effects. This method of separate assessment fails to capture the interconnectedness of natural systems, thereby lacking in realism.

Functioning primarily as a modelling framework, Tools4MSP provides a standardized structure for the CEA process. It identifies relationships between relevant concepts and outlines a systematic method for combining and interpreting results from multiple models. In summary, the impact chains are modelled through two distinct but interconnected tasks, namely pressures assessment and effects/impacts assessment (Figure 4.1).

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Figure 4.1. Exemplification of the Tools4MSP cumulative effects assessment (CEA) module (top) and interactive interface to CEA Case Study setup (bottom).

The framework offers flexibility in integrating various pressure models, but it is crucial to prioritize models that establish a connection, including spatial relationships, between the pressure and the corresponding human activity causing it. The Tools4MSP framework employs two models for pressure estimation:

- **Isotropic Convolution Model:** This serves as the basic model, applied by default when more accurate models are not applicable. It utilizes the spatial distribution of anthropogenic uses in the study area and pressure weights as input parameters.
- **Pressure Assessment of MARine Activities (PMAR) Model:** This model employs Lagrangian particle tracking algorithms to generate mid-quality representations of how pressures from human activities spread. A detailed presentation of this model can be found in section 4.2.1.

Additionally, outcomes from external pressure-specific models can be directly incorporated. This often improves assessment quality, particularly when default models do not meet the specific analysis objectives adequately. For example, modelling underwater noise propagation typically involves dedicated and complex models that consider principles of acoustics, accounting for factors such as sound wave behaviour, attenuation, and the influence of environmental factors on sound propagation.

Within the MSP4BIO project, enhancements have been made to the CEA Tools4MSP. These improvements focus on advancing the graphical interfaces to enhance functionality and user intuitiveness. This includes refining the configuration process for case studies and optimizing interactive interfaces for result consultation. Additionally, a notable enhancement involves introducing a new pressure modelling model specifically designed for climate change. This model relies on climate change velocity, and its development encompasses both the conceptual framework and the software development of the integrated module, extending the capabilities of the existing two models.

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4.2.2.2 PlanWise4Blue

The PlanWise4Blue (PW4B) platform, accessible at <https://gis.sea.ee/bluebiosites/>, is a collaborative initiative led by the Department of Marine Systems at the Estonian Marine Institute, University of Tartu. This innovative decision support system was born out of a critical need to bridge the gap between scientific research and policymaking. It aims to facilitate the sustainable development of marine areas and the formulation of effective conservation strategies for European seas, particularly in the context of rapid human-induced environmental change. The platform is dynamic, constantly expanding in geographical scope and incorporating different natural values, human impacts and analytical tools.

The PW4B portal is developed using ASP.NET MVC architecture, PostgreSQL database engine for data management, and ESRI ArcGIS API for JavaScript for geospatial data visualization and mapping. The PW4B technology ensures full responsiveness and accessibility across various devices, including smartphones, tablets, and computers, regardless of the operating system used (Windows, iOS, or Android). The development approach of PW4B is characterised by the use of the Single Page Application (SPA) model, which enables dynamic user interaction with the portal's controls, data, and elements within a single webpage, eliminating the need for page reloads after each action. This approach improves the user experience by enabling seamless navigation and interaction within the portal. The backend of PW4B uses PL/pgSQL Procedural Language to create and manage conditional and impact matrix tables, which are essential to the tool's ability to process and present data. Python programming language is used to analyse data, generate various human pressure combinations, and calculate the cumulative effects of different pressures on natural assets. The PW4B system architecture comprises server and client/user interface components. GIS data is prepared, analysed, and stored in a geodatabase using ArcGIS Desktop and Python

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scripts on the server side. ArcGIS Server enables the sharing of GIS data through Web Map Services (WMS) and the execution of Geoprocessing tool Services. Additionally, the PostgreSQL database is used to store and manage auxiliary tables such as conditional and impact matrix tables, WMS layer information, model parameters, and user interface configurations using PL/pgSQL. The ESRI ArcGIS API for JavaScript is used on the client side to visualize WMS layers and support interactive map creation. Users can overlay multiple layers, query feature information, and engage with the portal to set model parameters, execute geoprocessing services, and view the results. The PW4B portal facilitates the organization and management of geospatial data, ensuring interoperability. It serves as a versatile platform for creating customized scenarios, running diverse analyses, and supporting sustainable marine spatial planning (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2. Basic configuration of PlanWise4Blue portal and based technology used in development.

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PW4B comprises a suite of tools designed to provide insights into various ecological and economic aspects that are crucial for spatial planning and sustainable development in marine environments. Despite the complexity of the underlying algorithms, which capture the interactions between natural ecosystems and human activities, PW4B has a user-friendly interface. This design enables users regardless of their technical background to use these advanced methods. The platform effectively translates complex mathematical results into simple, accessible formats, streamlining the integration of scientific knowledge into policy and decision-making.

PW4B is currently available in three different versions: PW4B Estonia (https://gis.sea.ee/pw4b/adrienne/IL_map), PW4B North-East Baltic Sea (https://gis.sea.ee/pw4b/adrienne_gof/IL_map) and PW4B Baltic Sea (https://gis.sea.ee/pw4b/marea/ess_map). Each version presents tools and results from different projects with Estonian and regional implications, tailored to the needs of specific partners, stakeholders and funding bodies. Efforts are underway to merge these versions into a single application that will include existing and future tools and products.

The platform integrates the latest maps of natural assets, from species and habitats to ecosystem services. These maps are generated using the best available biological and environmental data from national and regional monitoring programs, European data infrastructures such as Copernicus, and scientific publications. Advanced machine learning algorithms such as Boosted Regression Trees, Random Forests and Generalized Additive Models are used to model and map these natural assets, providing spatially explicit results.

In assessing the cumulative effects of human activities on marine ecosystems, PW4B's CEA tool is a key feature. Opposing to other CEA tools, the PW4B goes beyond traditional expert-based assessments by using the latest scientific knowledge to quantitatively assess the individual and combined impacts of human activities on natural values. This

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approach, detailed in Kotta et al. (2020) and further exemplified in Vaher et al. (2022), uses a meta-analytical method to statistically determine the total impact of human activities and the sensitivity of nature values. Although data limitations currently exist for many combinations of nature values and pressure interactions, it is expected that this challenge will be significantly reduced in the near future. The knowledge base, including experimental evidence, on the interactive effects of various human activities on natural environments is growing exponentially.

Users can prepare new scenarios in PW4B by creating a workspace and defining a specific study area in the Baltic Sea region. The platform allows the selection of different natural values and human pressures to be included in the CEA. These pressures can represent current conditions or future management scenarios, with options for users to modify them to explore different spatial arrangements of human activities. After completing these inputs, users can view the results of the CEA (Figure 4.3).

During the MSP4BIO project, the integration of HELCOM data layers into the PW4B tool environment was a major step forward. This integration facilitated increased synergy between PW4B and HELCOM's State and Pressures of the Baltic Sea (SPIA) tool. For further details on the SPIA tool, please refer to the following subsection.

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Figure 4.3. Cumulative effects assessment results display on PlanWise4Blue portal.

4.2.2.3 HELCOM SPIA Tool

HELCOM SPIA tool enables the computation of spatial pressure and impact assessments utilizing the data layers employed in the HELCOM third holistic assessment (HOLAS 3) of the Baltic Sea. These data layers consist of 17 aggregated pressure layers and 57 ecosystem component layers. Users can perform pressure or impact calculations by utilizing all available data layers or by selecting specific combinations of layers. The tool employs sensitivity scores derived from the HOLAS 3 SPIA assessment but also permits users to make edits to these scores. Within the tool, users can explore the available pressure and ecosystem component layers in the map viewer, access metadata descriptions, and modify sensitivity scores. Additionally, users can run pressure and

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impact calculations using input data and sensitivity scores of their choice, examine the results in the map viewer, including insights into the contribution of human activities, pressures, and ecosystem components to the impact, and download the result raster and statistics matrix. The tool encompasses the Spatial Impact Index (SII), which assesses the spatial distribution of cumulative effects in the Baltic Sea, taking into account sensitivity scores for pressure-ecosystem combinations. The Baltic Sea Impact Index (BSII) quantifies holistic impact across all layers. The Spatial Pressure Index (SPI) calculates cumulative pressures from human activities in the Baltic Sea, leveraging aggregated pressure layers weighted by ecosystem component sensitivity scores to prevent overestimation of widespread, low-effect pressures. The Baltic Sea Pressure Index (BSPI) assesses cumulative pressure across all aggregated pressure layers. Both the SII and SPI adhere to the concepts introduced by Halpern et al. (2008), calculating the sum of pressures or impacts in 1x1 km assessment units (Figure 4.4).

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Figure 4.4. Distribution of potential cumulative effects from human activities on the Baltic Sea environment, based on the Baltic Sea Impact Index. The analysis is based on currently best available regional data, but spatial gaps may occur in some underlying datasets, as described by the data availability maps, showing available data for human activities/pressures (HA and PL) and ecosystem components (EC).

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4.2.3 Climate change impact assessment tools

4.2.3.1 PlanWise4Blue

The North-East Baltic Sea version of PW4B, available at https://gis.sea.ee/pw4b/adrienne_gof/IL_map, is designed to integrate climate change scenarios into its CEA. These scenarios are further combined with nutrient management strategies.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the newly developed PW4B algorithm, which can assess both individual and combined impacts of human activities on different natural assets, the CEA tool integrates four plausible scenarios:

1. Current climate and nutrient loading: This scenario reflects existing climate conditions and current levels of nutrient loading.
2. Current climate and nutrient reduction: In line with the HELCOM Maximum Allowable Inputs (MAI) target (<https://helcom.fi/baltic-sea-action-plan/nutrient-reduction-scheme/>), this scenario maintains current climate conditions while implementing nutrient load reductions.
3. Future Climate and Current Nutrient Load: This scenario projects future climate conditions while maintaining current nutrient load levels.
4. Future climate and nutrient reduction: This scenario combines expected future climate changes with nutrient load reductions in line with the HELCOM MAI target.

The PW4B adopted a different approach to assess the effects of climate change on the marine environment, departing from the widely used Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) scenarios (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Representative_Concentration_Pathway). Given the current uncertainty in directly correlating RCP scenarios with marine conditions, we

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examined the last 20 years of historical data to identify what could be considered a 'normal' year versus a 'future climate' year based on atmospheric variables such as air temperature, cloudiness and wind speed. Using the Copernicus marine hindcast data sets, we then created composite maps to represent typical ocean conditions for these categorically different years.

This environmental dataset served as the foundation for predicting the potential distribution of natural values, which act as indicators for both current and prospective future marine assets. These predictive maps were integrated into the PW4B portal to assess the cumulative impacts of current and future scenarios. This approach provides a more immediate, empirically-based understanding of marine environmental conditions, providing actionable insights for near-term planning and reducing the uncertainty often associated with long-term RCP-based projections.

To carry out analyses of the effects of climate change, it is essential to have map layers representing different nature values. Fortunately, the increasing availability of such map layers makes it possible to carry out a wide range of different scenario analyses (Figure 4.5).

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Figure 4.5. Display of cumulative effects assessment tool on the PlanWise4Blue portal, with an additional module to integrate nutrient management and climate change scenarios into the analysis.

4.2.3.2 Tools4MSP

This section introduces the tool currently being developed within the Tools4MSP infrastructure for the calculation of analog-based velocities, a crucial metric for effective adaptation planning in the face of climate change. Carroll et al. (2015) provided seminal

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insights into the identification of areas vulnerable to climate change through the concept of Biotic and Climatic Velocity. This framework emphasizes the contrasting vulnerabilities of different ecosystems and regions based on the rate at which they are expected to experience changes in climatic conditions.

Figure 4.6 presents a conceptual diagram comparing four types of velocity metrics for climate adaptation planning, with the methodology used in our tool. Specifically, the tool employs a nearest-neighbour approach to identify climatically analogous sites, focusing on the entire Mediterranean basin as the focal region. The tool calculates the analog-based velocities by determining the actual distance, in kilometres per year, between two climatically similar locations. Both forward and backward velocities are computed for each site (grid cell). The forward velocity measures the rate at which one must transition from a location with current climatic conditions to the closest site projected to exhibit similar conditions in the future. Elevated forward velocities signal a notable risk to species, suggesting potential challenges in adapting to swiftly evolving environmental circumstances. In contrast, the backward velocity gauges the pace required to revert to a site with anticipated future climatic conditions, originating from the nearest location currently sharing the same climatic conditions. Higher backward velocities indicate potential risks to the stability of the site.

Figure 4.6. Conceptual diagram comparing four types of velocity metrics used in climate adaptation planning (figure extracted from Carroll et al., 2015).

The steps to calculate analog-based velocities, as illustrated in Figure 4.7, are outlined as follows:

1. Define Analysis Area: The first step involves delineating the analysis area, preferably as a closed basin such as the Mediterranean, to mitigate edge effects.
2. Cell Division: The analysis area is then subdivided into regular cells to facilitate calculations.
3. Bioclimatic Variables Calculation: Bioclimatic variables, acting as predictors, are computed for both current conditions and future projections within each cell. In the

example provided, these variables were derived for two 25-year periods (2006–2030) and (2031–2055), although standard climate periods typically span 30 years. The dataset utilized includes nine bioclimatic variables related to Sea Surface Temperature (SST), specifically:

- a. Annual Mean Temperature
 - b. Annual Mean Diurnal Range
 - c. Isothermality
 - d. Temperature Seasonality
 - e. Max Temperature of Warmest Month
 - f. Min Temperature of Coldest Month
 - g. Annual Temperature Range
 - h. Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter
 - i. Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter
4. PCA: A PCA is automatically conducted on the combined space of the nine bioclimatic variables, considering both present and future conditions.
 5. Distance Matrix Calculation: Two distance matrices are computed: one pertaining to cells closest to current climatic conditions (for forward velocity) and another for cells nearest to future climatic conditions (for backward velocity).
 6. Introduction of Thresholds: Thresholds are introduced with respect to the climatic distances on the PCA space to ascertain similar climatic conditions.
 7. Velocity Maps Calculation: Subsequently, maps corresponding to forward velocities and backward velocities are generated.

Figure 4.7. Conceptual framework of the velocity calculation tool being integrated into the Tools4MSP infrastructure.

During the implementation phase of the Tools4MSP infrastructure, a prototype tool named CCV was utilized to calculate analog-based velocities for the Mediterranean Sea region. The results obtained from this prototype are illustrated in Figure 4.8, showcasing both forward velocity (top) and backward velocity (bottom).

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Figure 4.8. Initial findings showcasing the computation of analog-based velocities for the Mediterranean region: forward velocity (top) and backward velocity (bottom) (Tools4MSP prototype tool).

The analysis reveals that the mean velocity for the Mediterranean Sea is approximately 5 km/year. In contrast, the mean velocity for the Adriatic Sea is notably higher, at approximately 14 km/year. A significant result emerges, indicating that 16% of the cells within the Adriatic Sea lack analog-based sites within the Mediterranean Sea. This implies

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that climatic conditions present in approximately 16% of the Adriatic Sea cells will not have analogs within the Mediterranean Sea in the future.

These preliminary results offer valuable insights into the projected climatic dynamics within the Mediterranean and Adriatic Seas. The higher mean velocity observed in the Adriatic Sea suggests a greater rate of climatic change in this region compared to the broader Mediterranean basin. Furthermore, the identification of cells lacking analog-based sites underscores the potential vulnerability of certain areas within the Adriatic Sea to future climatic shifts.

It is important to note that these results are purely demonstrative and indicative. The model utilized in this analysis has not yet been fully calibrated. As such, these findings should be interpreted with caution, and further refinement and calibration of the model are necessary to obtain more accurate and reliable results. Despite their preliminary nature, the results obtained from the CCV prototype offer a glimpse into the potential utility of analog-based velocity calculations for climate adaptation planning within the Tools4MSP infrastructure. Moving forward, continued refinement and calibration of the model will be essential to harness the full potential of this tool in informing adaptive management strategies for the Mediterranean and Adriatic Seas.

4.2.4 Prioritization tools

The MSP4BIO project achieved a significant milestone with the development and integration of a prioritisation tool into the PW4B platform, which is currently in a testing phase. The tool is named the Area-based Conservation Planner (ABC, https://gis.sea.ee/pw4b/prioritizer/workspaces_tabs). This tool leverages the capabilities of the R package 'prioritizr' (<https://prioritizr.net/>), which is adept at efficiently solving conservation planning problems. Prioritizr supports a wide range of objectives, constraints and penalties, allowing the customization of conservation planning solutions to meet the specific needs of a given conservation initiative. The systematic and evidence-based

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approach of these tools enhances the transparency, inclusiveness and defensibility of the conservation decision-making process.

A typical conservation planning exercise begins with the delineation of a study area, encompassing all regions relevant to the decision maker or the hypothesis under investigation. This area is then divided into discrete segments, called planning units, each representing an independently manageable portion of the study area. The aim is to identify a combination of these units for conservation action, such as the establishment of protected areas or habitat restoration.

Data on the biodiversity elements of interest are essential for these exercises, and the nature value maps within PW4B are used here. In addition, cost data play a crucial role, providing insight into the relative costs associated with managing each planning unit for conservation purposes.

The next stage is to define the conservation planning problem and its solution. The prioritisation tool helps to construct and solve these problems. Solutions are derived by formulating a mathematical optimization problem based on planning unit data, cost data and environmental feature data, and aligned with the overall objectives of the prioritisation. In general, the objective function in this optimization problem aims to minimize certain aspects (such as the cost of the solution) or maximize others (such as the number of environmental features preserved).

The PW4B ABC tool is designed to facilitate flexible and effective conservation planning by allowing users to input various parameters and data, which are then used to generate optimized conservation strategies.

User input and data preparation: Users can define different inputs. These inputs include decisions on whether to consider human impacts as exclusions, the use of boundary constraints, the cost of planning area units and a time limit for the solver. In addition,

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users provide data on natural values, including their identifiers, relative protection targets and protection costs. The tool uses user-selected layers for natural values and human activities.

Data processing and problem formulation: The tool then processes the input data, creating planning units and integrating cost data. It also processes the human impact layers by determining which pixels in the planning area are affected by human activities. The nature value layers are then read and used in the conservation planning problem.

Optimization problem and solution: The core of the analysis is the definition and solution of the optimization problem. The problem is formulated differently depending on the user's choice of boundary conditions. The 'prioritizr' package is used to set objectives (such as minimizing costs or maximizing the number of environmental features conserved), define binary choices and apply constraints based on human impact. The solver, guided by the time constraints and other parameters, then finds an optimal solution.

Results and output: Once the optimization problem has been solved, the tool generates outputs, including a raster map showing protected and unprotected areas (Figure 4.9). This map is saved as a GeoTIFF file. In addition, the tool provides summaries of the selected areas, including the total area protected, the cost of protection, and the coverage of natural values within the protected areas. These summaries provide valuable insights into the effectiveness and efficiency of the conservation strategy.

In summary, this PW4B ABC tool offers a cutting-edge analysis environment for conservation planning, allowing users to input a variety of data and parameters to generate tailored conservation strategies. Its integration into other PW4B tools enhances the platform's ability to support informed and effective conservation decision making (e.g., using CEA in the designation of protected areas).

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Figure 4.9. Display of prioritisation tool on the PlanWise4Blue portal, with an additional module to integrate cumulative effects assessment into the analysis.

5. Improving decision-making through the use of tools in the case study areas

In section 4.2, a comprehensive set of digital tools updated and upgraded in the frame of MSP4BIO to address the most pressing demands of the project CS. These tools were developed to aid decision-making processes for conservation planning and spatial management within the MSP4BIO CS. This diverse set of tools provides solutions for the assessment of connectivity, the assessment of the (cumulative) effects of human pressures and climate change on marine ecosystems and the identification and prioritization of EBSAs to inform the design and implementation of area-based conservation measures in the context of MPA processes and MSP. The integration of

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these tools provides a way to more accurately identify important ecological features, evaluate the environmental impacts of both local and transboundary pressures, address underlying uncertainties, and effectively assess the impact of potential management strategies and blue growth scenarios. This approach enables a strategic consolidation of information and resources, aimed at optimizing decision-making processes. The ESE1 toolkit empowers stakeholders to make well-informed decisions that align with the objectives of sustainability and conservation of marine ecosystems. This ultimately contributes to the enhanced preservation and sustainable management of marine environments.

The PW4B, Tools4MSP, and HELCOM SPIA Tool, along with most of their underlying and associated applications, are the outcomes of extensive iterative processes developed through a wide range of projects, including MSP4BIO, as well as various national and regional implementations. These efforts have culminated in the creation of user-friendly, fully functional and stable tools that effectively address the needs of their respective domains. The continuous refinement and collaboration across diverse projects have ensured that these tools are not only robust but also tailored to meet the practical demands of stakeholders and end-users. With the exception of the analog-based velocities application for the assessment of climate change effects, which is in the process of being implemented in Tools4MSP, all other applications presented in section 4.2 are fully available for their implementation through open-access web-based applications (see Table 1 for information on expected users).

The following section shows how a comprehensive set of tools can be used in the Baltic Sea test site to improve conservation planning and management. The first step is to define specific management questions, which can vary widely. For example, current cumulative effects within existing MPAs could be assessed to determine whether pressures exceed tolerance thresholds for key nature values. This analysis could then be extended to

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consider future climate scenarios and assess potential spatial shifts in key natural values or changes in their tolerance levels due to climate change, assuming other human pressures remain constant. Such assessments could indicate whether our current MPAs are sustainable and identify measures to improve their sustainability.

There may also be interest in identifying marine areas for further MPA designation. To do this in a sustainable way, it is important to establish whether current conservation targets are achievable, i.e., whether there are sufficient nature values within the area of interest. It is also important to determine whether these valuable areas are under pressure from multiple human activities that could prevent the development of a new protected area. It is also important to understand the extent to which climate change may alter the nature values in these areas, as such changes could make conservation efforts more difficult.

In order to carry out conservation analysis effectively, it is important to identify specific priorities, which involves scoping specific management needs. This entails defining the overall context and identifying ecological issues, which may involve prioritising particular species, habitats or areas. Prioritisation requires adherence to principles derived from factors such as uniqueness, aggregation, fitness consequences, resilience and naturalness.

In the analysis step, for example, the focus could be on the intensity of different ecosystem services (regulating and provisioning) provided by underwater species and habitats, and the assessment of the cumulative effects of human pressures on these services under current environmental conditions and future climate scenarios. This analysis can be carried out using the Baltic Sea section of the PlanWise4Blue tool. Users start by defining a new scenario, specifying the extent, priority natural values (in this case selected ecosystem services) and human uses (Figure 5.1). The human use scenario can reflect existing pressures in the region, or users can customise their scenario. After completing these preliminary steps, users can choose to run the assessment under

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current or future climate conditions. The portal then processes the scenario and the results are displayed on two maps for easy comparison of the initial and final distribution of natural values, including any shifts in these values (Figure 5.2). Users also have the option of juxtaposing these shifts with an uncertainty assessment of the changes.

Figure 5.1. Presentation of the cumulative effects assessment tool landing page within the PlanWise4Blue portal, where users can define analyses and scenario settings.

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Figure 5.2. Display of the results of the CEA tool, which assesses the cumulative impacts of current human use scenarios on the quality of herring spawning habitats. The left panel shows the condition of the spawning grounds in the absence of pressure, while the right panel shows their quality under the influence of these pressures.

In another analysis aimed at designing a new protected area, the data collection focuses on ecological issues and follows a prioritisation analysis to define the conservation objective. The initial analysis examines whether the area of interest can support the ambitious conservation goals set. This analysis can be carried out using the ABC tool within the PlanWise4Blue platform. Similar to the CEA tool, users need to specify the size of the area, the natural values present and the human use scenario (Figure 5.3). In this section, users can assess the feasibility of the conservation objective. Given the computational demands of the prioritisation analysis, such a preliminary assessment is necessary to save time.

Figure 5.3. Introduction to the ABC tool landing page on the PlanWise4Blue portal, where users can set analysis parameters and scenario settings. This interface allows users to select specific natural values, identify human pressures (from existing conditions or hypothetical scenarios) and determine the method by which the prioritisation tool

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calculates areas. The tool offers three analysis options: no boundary constraints, small boundary constraints and large boundary constraints.

The result of the conservation target analysis provides insight into the total proportionate area covered by the nature values of interest and the proportionate area of these values that remain unaffected by the pressures outlined in the scenario. This latter assessment is critical in determining whether the proposed MPA scenario is feasible or whether the environmental impacts of certain pressures need to be mitigated prior to designation. In addition, this section allows for the specification of conservation targets for each natural value, along with associated conservation costs (Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.4. Presentation of the results of the conservation target analysis, providing insight into the total proportionate area covered by the nature values of interest and the proportionate area of these values unaffected by the scenario pressures. It also allows users to set specific conservation targets and associated costs for each natural asset.

Once these steps have been completed, users can initiate analyses to determine the spatial configuration of the most appropriate conservation area on the basis of the current scenario (Figure 5.5). Similarly, these analyses can be run under future climate conditions to assess the sustainability of future marine protected areas (MPAs) in the light of expected climate change. The results can then be evaluated, allowing even more detailed analyses to be carried out to precisely address the conservation issues under

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investigation. This process facilitates the identification of optimal solutions and mitigation strategies to reduce the cumulative effects of human pressures.

Figure 5.5. Presentation of the results of the prioritisation tool on the PlanWise4Blue portal, evaluating the most beneficial conservation area according to the chosen scenario.

6. Conclusions and food-for-thought

The Ecological Toolkit (ESE1) developed by the MSP4BIO project represents a significant step forward in the design, establishment and management of MPAs. By improving decision-making processes with a focus on prioritising areas, integrating connectivity processes and assessing human impacts on marine ecosystems, the toolkit follows the step-by-step guidance of the ESE framework. This comprehensive approach, integrating ecological data, hydrodynamic models and climate change considerations, aims to address the multiple pressures on marine ecosystems and promote sustainable marine conservation strategies that respond to the challenges of climate change and human activities.

The assessment of existing DSTs across Europe revealed their varying abilities to contribute to the design and management of MPAs. While none of the identified DSTs alone could cover all the ecological and environmental dimensions required for MPA design and management, their collective application holds promise for comprehensive planning and decision-making in major European sea basins. The tools identified, particularly those developed for the Baltic Sea, but also including promising tools for the North Sea and the Mediterranean, demonstrate the potential of DSTs to inform the identification, prioritisation and management of ecologically or biologically significant areas, despite the current lack of a single tool that addresses all relevant dimensions.

Recent developments within the MSP4BIO project have significantly enhanced selected DSTs, in particular CEA's Tools4MSP and PW4B, with a focus on CEA, prioritisation and climate change adaptation. These developments, including improved interfaces and the introduction of a new climate change pressure modelling model, underline the potential of DSTs to support adaptive management strategies. The integration of HELCOM data layers into PW4B and the development of the Area-based Conservation Planner are

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further examples of progress in creating tools that facilitate flexible and effective conservation planning.

However, the integration of functional connectivity into existing DSTs remains an area for further development. Despite progress in addressing cumulative impacts, prioritisation and climate change, effective consideration of functional connectivity is essential for comprehensive environmental planning and management. Future efforts must focus on improving DSTs to incorporate these critical aspects and ensure that the tools provide robust and ecologically meaningful insights for adaptive management strategies in the face of climate change. This direction will ensure the development of DSTs that are not only comprehensive in scope, but also dynamic and responsive to the evolving needs of MPA and MSP processes.

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Annex A

Table A1. Stakeholders needs, issues, and topics to be answered through the practices. Notes about the scoping and other practices are also reported. The Stakeholder needs have been proposed by each case study or through the project activities (column = origin). The ESE1 (Ecological Toolkit) description in the present deliverable on considers Practices from 1 to 4.

Stakeholder needs/issues/ topics to be answered	Practice 1 - Scoping	Practice 2 - Data and repr.n	Practice 3 - Analysis and diagn.	Practice 4 – Prioritiz. and design	Practice 5 - Management	Practice 6 - Monitoring	Notes in relation to the application of the scoping (practice 1) and others	Origin of the stakeholder needs/issues/ topics
What monitoring approach could be taken to evaluate conservation measures for extensive MPA networks?	x	x	x			x	Firstly, decide the monitoring objectives in relation to the conservation objectives with the scoping	5.2 Azores L1
What monitoring approach could be taken to evaluate conservation measures for extensive offshore MPA networks?	x	x	x			x	Firstly, decide the monitoring objectives in relation to the conservation objectives with the scoping	5.2 Azores L1
How can we take into consideration	x						In the scoping, the conservation	5.2 Azores L2

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the conservation of OECM within MSP implementation if there are no legally binding instruments?							challenge is formulated.	
How to deal with the knowledge gaps related to water column data to support decision-making for conservation measures offshore?	x	x					Define the data potentially needed to characterize the water column in relation to the targets of conservation and conservation features of the case study area in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Azores L2
How can we effectively manage in an integrated way the conservation unit PNI which has both terrestrial and marine components for marine birds?	x	x	x	x	x	x	Define PNI, define marine and terrestrial conservation features to include in the practices through the scoping	5.2 Azores L3
How can we adapt to climate change within our MPA?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the targets of conservation and the conservation features in the scoping (p1)	5.2 Baltic Sea L1, NW Med CoP test site hierarchization

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How to analyse the main conflict areas between human uses and environment?	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation of the case study area with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Baltic Sea L2
How to identify the main conflict areas between human uses and environment?	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and features, and the human uses and other potential pressures to be included in the conflict analysis with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Baltic Sea L2
How should the accuracy of the spatial data for MPAs identification be improved?	x	x					Accuracy and reliability can be assessed in relation to a well-formulated conservation problem - through the scoping (pr.1) and practice 2	5.2 Black Sea L1
How should the reliability of the spatial data for MPAs identification be improved?	x	x					Accuracy and reliability can be assessed in relation to a well-formulated conservation problem - through the scoping (pr.1) and practice 2	5.2 Black Sea L1
How to anticipate climate change	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and conservation	5.2 Black Sea L1

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effects in the MPA network?							features in relation of the case study area with the scoping (pr.1)	
How to assess compatibility of maritime uses and MPA conservation objectives considering the local context?	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation of the case study area with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L1
How to evaluate cumulative impacts in MSP and MPA?	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and features, and the human uses and other potential pressures to be included in the analysis of cumulative impacts in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L1
What will be the extent of a new MPA to reach the 30-by-30 target?	x	x	x	x			Define the conservation targets and features targeted with the MPA with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L1
How can vulnerable species be protected against climatic stressors?	x	x	x	x	x		Identify conservation targets and species to be considered in the analysis in the scoping (p1)	5.2 Black Sea L2
How do the impacts of	x	x	x					5.2 Black Sea L2

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permitted activities in the MPA affect keystones species?								
How to evaluate economic impacts of conservation measures?	x						This is not an issue that can be strictly answered with the ESE1 practices, but the scoping can help in characterizing the conservation measures	5.2 Black Sea L2
How to evaluate trade-offs in MSP and MPA?	x						The scoping is essential to define the trade-offs among what in specific. As it is now, this issue is generic	5.2 Black Sea L2
How to get data on cumulative impacts of different activities or of an activity concentrated in one zone?	x	x	x				Before generically searching for data, define the targets of conservation and features, and the human uses and other potential pressures to be included in the analysis of cumulative impacts in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L2
How to get proper sustainability	x						Define "sustainability criteria" with the	5.2 Black Sea L2

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criteria for maritime uses?							scoping by focusing on the legal framework and conservation targets from multiple legal sources	
How to measure the compensations?	x	x	x	x	x		Supposedly, planners will need to have defined a potential set of spatial designation and management actions for conservation that need to be compensated (for instance, through running practices 1-5). The analysis of compensation is not strictly the focus of ESE1	5.2 Black Sea L2
How to prioritize areas to be protected according to climate change?	x	x	x	x			Define the characteristics, key features and conservation targets of the targeted key study area in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L2
What are the environmental legislation or criteria guidelines for MPA identification and	x						This can be answered with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L2

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designation, including socio-economic criteria (Commission's SWD, EU Directives, IUSN, new criteria UNCLOS)?								
How to prioritize existing MPA network evolution according to climate change?	x	x	x	x			Define the characteristics, key features and conservation targets of the targeted key study area in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L2 linked to row 119
How to analyse the main conflict areas that may arise if we need to expand MPA in response to ecological connectivity?	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation of the case study area with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L3
How to analyse the main conflict areas that may arise if we need to expand MPA in response to other valuable environmental assets?	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation of the case study area with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L3
How to analyse the main conflict areas that may	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and conservation	5.2 Black Sea L3

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arise if we need to expand MPA in response to sensitive habitats?							features in relation of the case study area with the scoping (pr.1)	
How to anticipate the change in biotope?	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation of the biotope the case study area with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L3
How to identify sheltered areas?	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and conservation features to be considered for identifying "shelters" in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L3
How to identify the main conflict areas that may arise if we need to expand MPA in response to other valuable environmental assets?	x	x	x	x			Define the targets of conservation and features, and the human uses and other potential pressures to be included in the conflict analysis with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L3/Baltic Sea L3
How to identify the main conflict areas that may arise if we need to expand MPA in response to sensitive habitats?	x	x	x	x			Define the targets of conservation and features, and the human uses and other potential pressures to be included in the	5.2 Black Sea L3/Baltic Sea L3

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							conflict analysis with the scoping (pr.1)	
How to identify the main conflict areas that may arise if we need to expand MPA to include ecological connectivity?	x	x	x	x			Define the targets of conservation and features, and the human uses and other potential pressures to be included in the conflict analysis with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 Black Sea L3/Baltic Sea L3
How to address the different scales of management (MSP or MPA) in an ESE framework	x						With the scoping the issue can be formulated with respect to a case study.	5.2 Cadiz L1
How to assess the ecosystems providing the ES that are connected to the socio-economic criteria listed as high priority?	x	x	x				With the scoping, planners can frame the topic of ES depending on the case study	5.2 Cadiz L1
How to monitor the ecosystems providing the ES that are connected to the socio-economic criteria listed as high priority?	x	x	x			x	Practices 1-3 can be applied to identify the ES and then monitoring targeting the ecosystem providing the ES	5.2 Cadiz L1

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							can be monitored (pr. 6)	
How can we improve the protection of pelagic habitats?	x	x	x				Define key conservation features and targets in the scoping (p1)	5.2 North Sea L1
How to prioritize space use within a multi-use MPA?	x	x	x	x			Define the characteristics, key features and conservation targets of the targeted MPA in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 North Sea L1
How to take into account climate change to improve the protection of pelagic habitats?	x	x	x	x	x		Define pelagic habitats characteristics and components in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 North Sea L1
How to take into account climate change to prioritise space use within a multi-use MPA?	x	x	x	x			Define the characteristics, key features and conservation targets of the targeted MPA in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 North Sea L1
How can an MPA be used as a living lab?	x	x					Identify MPA targets and features in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 North Sea L2
How to take into account climate change to prioritise areas for protecting pelagic biodiversity?	x	x	x				Although this issue mentions climate change, the question is related to the knowledge needed to understand potential climate-induced	5.2 North Sea L2,

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							changes. Define pelagic habitats characteristics and components in the scoping (pr.1)	
How can we prioritise a location for the designation of MPA?	x	x	x	x			Define key conservation features and targets in the scoping (p1)	5.2 North Sea L3
How can climate change help identify which areas are suitable for oyster restoration? (Reformulation: what areas are suitable for oyster reef restoration in the context of a changing climate?)	x	x	x	x			This question can be answered by identifying all the suitable areas (practice 3), and also by prioritizing among suitable areas (practice 4) to achieve a specific conservation target (to be defined in the scoping practice, in case)	5.2 North Sea L3
What tools can we use to implement spatial protection of pelagic habitats?	x	x					Tools and methods selection depends on data availability and the capacity of the planning team. These aspects are assessed in the Practices 1 and 2	5.2 North Sea L3
Where are suitable areas for oyster reef restoration?	x	x	x					5.2 North Sea L3

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Which criteria use to prioritise a location for the designation of MPA?	x	x	x	x			Define the conservation targets and features for the prioritization exercise with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 North Sea L3
Which tool use to prioritise a location for the designation of MPA?	x	x	x				Tools and methods selection depends on data availability and the capacity of the planning team. These aspects are assessed in the Practices 1 and 2	5.2 North Sea L3
How can pressures surrounding the location be considered? (supposed that the location is an existing MPA)	x	x	x				Identify MPA targets and features in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 North Sea L3 linked to row 38
How can we meet the 10% strictly protection target?	x	x	x	x			This question is generic. With the scoping it can be structured around the conservation features and targets for the scope of the analysis with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L1
How to achieve the strict Protection Area							Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation	5.2 NW Med L1

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Target (10% by 2030)?							to the geographical scope of the analysis with the scoping (pr.1)	
How to achieve the strict Protection Area Target (10% by 2030)?	x	x	x	x			Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation to the geographical scope of the analysis with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L1
How to assess the transboundary ecological coherence of the MPA network?	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation to the case study area with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L1
How to better address ecological functionalities in conservation objectives?	x						Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation to the case study area with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L1
Can we prioritise areas for protecting pelagic biodiversity?	x	x	x	x			Define pelagic biodiversity facets and components in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L2
How to develop scenarios to assess adequacy of the MPA network?	x	x	x				The scoping can help in defining what a climate smart MPA network is and what topics	5.2 NW Med L2

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							and criteria need to be considered in the subsequent practices	
How to develop scenarios to assess comprehensiveness of the MPA network?	x	x	x				The scoping can help in defining what a climate smart MPA network is and what topics and criteria need to be considered in the subsequent practices	5.2 NW Med L2
How to develop scenarios to assess connectivity of the MPA network?	x	x	x				The scoping can help in defining what a climate smart MPA network is and what topics and criteria need to be considered in the subsequent practices	5.2 NW Med L2
How to develop scenarios to assess representativeness of the MPA network?	x	x	x				The scoping can help in defining what a climate smart MPA network is and what topics and criteria need to be considered in the subsequent practices	5.2 NW Med L2
How to improve protection of Marine Mammals in coherence with	x	x	x	x	x			5.2 NW Med L2

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ongoing initiatives?								
How to protect deep VME?	x	x	x	x	x		Define deep VME with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L2
How to maintain population persistence across this transboundary MPA?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the characteristics, key features and conservation targets of the targeted population in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L2 based on D3.2 Connectivity Table
How to maintain population persistence within the MPA?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the characteristics, key features and conservation targets of the targeted population in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L2 based on D3.2 Connectivity Table
How can deep-water VME be more effectively conserved with regards to anthropogenic impacts arising from human activities in the NW Med?	x	x	x				Define deep-water VME in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L3
How can deep-water VME be more effectively identified with regards to anthropogenic	x	x	x				Define deep-water VME in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L3

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impacts arising from human activities in the NW Med?								
How can we minimise the impact of bottom- trawling on the growth of cold- water corals located in NWMed deep-water VME?	x	x	x			x	Define deep-water VME in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L3
How can we minimise the impact of bottom- trawling on the growth of gorgonians located in NWMed deep-water VME?	x	x	x			x	Define deep-water VME in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L3
How can we minimise the impact of bottom- trawling on the survival of cold- water corals located in NWMed deep-water VME?	x	x	x			x	Define deep-water VME in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L3
How can we minimise the impact of bottom- trawling on the survival of gorgonians	x	x	x			x	Define deep-water VME in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L3

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located in NWMed deep-water VME?								
How can we reduce anthropogenic impacts on key sensitive cetacean species?	x	x	x	x	x			5.2 NW Med L3
How to maintain community persistence across this transboundary MPA?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the characteristics, key features and conservation targets of the communities of the transboundary MPA in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L3
How to manage cross-border MPA for cetacean conservation?	x	x	x	x	x			5.2 NW Med L3
How to reduce collision risk?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the targeted conservation features and the study area with the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L3
Is there some structuration in the distribution of environmental stakes?	x						Define the environmental stakes in the scoping	5.2 NW Med L3
What is the impact of climate change on deep ecosystems in the NWMed?	x	x	x				Define conservation targets and feateures about deepsea	5.2 NW Med L3

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							ecosystems with the scoping (pr.1)	
How can we design conservation areas for the protection of cetacean to noise pollution, particularly during the breeding and feeding season and in sensitive areas?	x	x	x	x	x			5.2 NW Med L3 and D3.2 Table 7
How can we reduce the impact of sound pollution on key sensitive cetacean species?	x	x	x	x	x			5.2 NW Med L3 and D3.2 Table 7
How to maintain mobile species persistence?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the targets of conservation and mobile species and their characteristics in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L3 based on D3.2 Connectivity Table
How to maintain mobile species persistence across this transboundary MPA?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the targets of conservation and mobile species and their characteristics in the scoping (pr.1)	5.2 NW Med L3 based on D3.2 Connectivity Table
How to maintain population persistence?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the characteristics, key features and conservation targets of the targeted	5.2 NW Med L3 based on D3.2 Connectivity Table

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							population in the scoping (pr.1)	
Are VME connected across the Mediterranean Sea basin?	x	x	x				Define VME in the scoping phase	5.2 NW Med L3, 5.2 North Sea L2,
How to select planning units using habitat data only?	x	x	x	x			This issue is a not well formulated one. The problem is: what would you like to select planning unit for?	D3.2 Connectivity Table
How can we explore alternative MPA network designs?	x	x	x	x			Identify MPA targets and features in the scoping (pr.1)	D3.2 Connectivity Table
How can we assess trade-offs of different ecological decisions?	x	x	x				Frame the ecological decisions, with targets and conservation features in the scoping (p1)	D3.2 Connectivity Table
How can we connect fragmented seascapes?	x	x	x	x			Define the targets of conservation and the conservation features in the scoping (p1)	D3.2 Connectivity Table
How can we implement EC?	x						In the scoping, frame the conservation problem, define the target of conservation and	D3.2 Connectivity Table

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							the conservation features	
How can we optimize connectivity while protecting?	x	x	x	x	x		Through the scoping, the issue can be better formulated. The actions can include a spatial prioritization (p4) and management actions (p5)	D3.2 Connectivity Table
How can we regulate ecological connectivity?							Define key conservation features, habitat and species to characterize the case study area to identify what aspect of connectivity to consider	D3.2 Connectivity Table
How to maintain community persistence?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the characteristics, key features and conservation targets of the community in the scoping (pr.1)	D3.2 Connectivity Table
How to maintain local retention in MPA?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the targets of conservation and conservation features of the MPA to be managed in the scoping (pr.1)	D3.2 Connectivity Table
How can we protect threatened	x	x	x	x	x		Define key conservation	D3.2 Functional Diversity Table

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communities from human and climate change-related impacts?							features and targets for the ecological communities in the scoping (p1)	
How can we adapt conservation areas for the protection of cetacean to noise pollution, particularly during the breeding and feeding season and in sensitive areas?	x	x	x	x	x			D3.2 Table 7
How can we evaluate ecosystem effects of alternative fishing scenarios to explore alternative management strategies?	x	x	x					D3.2 Trophic Ecology Table
How can we protect ecosystem food web stability?	x	x	x	x	x		Through the scoping, the issue can be better formulated. The actions can include a spatial prioritization (p4) and management actions (p5)	D3.2 Trophic Ecology Table

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How to design a climate-smart MPA network?	x						The scoping can help in defining what a climate smart MPA network is and what topics and criteria need to be considered in the subsequent practices	D3.3
How to design a climate-smart MPA?	x						The scoping can help in defining what a climate smart MPA network is and what topics and criteria need to be considered in the subsequent practices	D3.3
How to identify future areas of interest for conservation integrating climate change?	x	x	x	x			Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in the scoping (pr.1)	D3.3
How to integrate climate change in management framing?	x					x	Define the targets of conservation and conservation features of the area to be managed in the scoping (pr.1)	D3.3
How to predict future fisheries grounds?	x	x	x					D3.3
How to predict the future of cod and	x	x	x					D3.3

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sprat nurseries in the Bay of Gdansk regarding climate change?								
How to protect habitats of priority for conservation in the context of climate change?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the characteristics, key features and conservation targets and the geographical scope of the analysis with the scoping (pr.1)	D3.3
Which areas to protect in order to achieve the 30-by-30 target?	x	x	x	x			Define the conservation targets and features with the scoping (pr.1)	D3.3
How can we effectively protect biodiversity and target species?	x						Define the targets and the conservation features in the scoping practice to ground the needs for the following practices	ESE_Worksheet
How sink and source areas for the target species can be identified?	x	x	x					ESE_Worksheet
How to sustainably manage a fish population at sea basin level	x	x	x	x	x			ESE_Worksheet

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What will be the extent of a new MPA?	x	x	x	x			Define the conservation targets and features targeted with the MPA with the scoping (pr.1)	ESE_Worksheet
Will the MPA cover the entire area, or will there be different zones with different management objectives?							This issue needs to be formulated in the context of the conservation targets of MPAs, which can be defined in the scoping (pr.1)	ESE_Worksheet
Does climate change influence the reef-former <i>Lanice conchilega</i> in the Belgian coastal area?	x	x	x					MIRO board North Sea
How do MPA policies intersect with MSP planners?	x						Issue to be formulated and set in the scoping practice	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization
How do sectoral policy objectives align with the goals of our MPA	x						Issue to be formulated and analysed in the scoping practice	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization
How should we address terrestrial impacts on our MPA?	x	x	x	x	x		Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation of the MPA with the scoping (pr.1)	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization
What protection needs have been	x						This question can be eanswered	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization

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agreed upon at the regional level for our MPA?							through the scoping on legislative framework	
How can we analyse the pressures facing our MPA?	x	x					Identify MPA targets and features in the scoping (pr.1)	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization
How can we effectively collect the necessary data to be used in area-based management tools?	x						With the scoping practice, planners clarify the targets of conservation, the conservation features from the legislation in the specific context to be effective	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization
Should our MPA have legally binding regulations or not	x	x	x	x	x		Depending of conservation objectives and features, the practices can be applied to identify zoning or management actions to achieve the targets of conservation. Subsequently, planners can decide about the suitable type of regulation sources to designate areas or actions	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization

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What are the data requirements for our MPA?	x						In the scoping, define the conservation problems and the conservation features	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization
What are the potential terrestrial impacts on our MPA?	x	x	x				Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation of the MPA with the scoping (pr.1)	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization
What monitoring strategies should we employ for our MPA	x	x	x			x	Firstly, decide the monitoring objectives in relation to the conservation objectives with the scoping	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization
How can the monitoring of the status of an area be conducted?	x	x				x	Define the targets of conservation for the specific location in the scoping (p1)	WP 2 Questions
How can we designate area-based management tools (ABMT, including MPA & OECM)?	x						With the scoping practice, planners clarify the targets of conservation, the conservation features from the legislation in the specific context	WP 2 Questions
How can we identify significant areas for conservation?	x						In the scoping, frame the conservation problem, define the	WP 2 Questions

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							target of conservation and the conservation features	
How can we identify significant ecological features for conservation?	x						In the scoping, frame the conservation problem, define the target of conservation and the conservation features	WP 2 Questions
Other stakeholder needs and issues								
What are the good practices on MSP-MPA integration in terms of governance authority?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Baltic Sea L3
How can be clarified the procedures for Portuguese MSP Plans to integrate newly classified MPA?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L1
How can we balance economic interests with the need for environmental protection within our MPA?							Not strictly the purpose of ESE1, but identifying the conservation needs within MPAs is the preliminary analysis for run the analysis	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization

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							with economic interests	
How can we better demonstrate the effectiveness of conservation measures to stakeholders?							Not strictly the purpose of this ESE1	5.2 Azores L2
How can we improve the integration of socio-economic objectives in the evaluation of new drawing MPA?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L1
How can we improve the integration of socio-economic objectives in the evaluation of the current MPA network?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L1
How can we improve the integration of socio-economic objectives in the re-drawing of the current MPA network?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L1
How do we deal with the profound knowledge gap in							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L2

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socio-economic data?								
How do we deal with the profound spatial dimensions' knowledge gap in socio-economic data?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L2
How to better include the evaluation of stakeholders' alignment in the MSP processes?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L1
How to better include the evaluation of stakeholders' expectations in the MSP processes?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L1
How to better include the evaluation of stakeholders' satisfaction level in the MSP processes?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L1
How to better integrate the extended MPA in the MSP plan?							"integration" needs to be defined in the issue. The scoping could help in this endeavour. Moreover, Define	5.2 Black Sea L1

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							the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation to the case study area with the scoping (practice 1)	
How to better integrate the extended MPA in the MSP process?							"integration" needs to be defined in the issue. The scoping could help in this endeavour. Moreover, Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation to the case study area with the scoping (practice 1)	5.2 Black Sea L1
How to better integrate the new established MPA in the MSP plan?							"integration" needs to be defined in the issue. The scoping could help in this endeavour. Moreover, Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation to the case study area with the scoping (practice 1)	5.2 Black Sea L1
How to better integrate the new							"integration" needs to be defined in the	5.2 Black Sea L1

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established MPA in the MSP process?							issue. The scoping could help in this endeavour. Moreover, Define the targets of conservation and conservation features in relation to the case study area with the scoping (practice 1)	
How to create a culture of collaboration among responsible institutions?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Cadiz L1
How to include the evaluation of stakeholders' alignment in the MSP processes?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L1
How to include the evaluation of stakeholders' expectations in the MSP processes?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Azores L1
How to transform participation in a cultural behaviour?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Cadiz L1
What are the compensations [for conservation actions]?							Supposedly, planners will need to have defined a potential set of	5.2 Black Sea L2

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							spatial designation and management actions for conservation that need to be compensated (for instance, through running practices 1-5). The analysis of compensation is not strictly the focus of ESE1	
What are the good practices on MSP-MPA integration in terms of governance authority?							Not the purpose of ESE1	5.2 Baltic Sea L3
What methods can we use to effectively involve stakeholders in the management of our MPA?							Not the purpose of ESE1	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization
What monitoring tool use to demonstrate the effectiveness of conservation measures to stakeholders?							Not the purpose of ESE1	MIRO board Azores,
What should we do if our MPA is not covered within							Not the purpose of ESE1	NW Med CoP test site hierarchization

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the MSP framework?								
What are the country level MPA-MSP integration?	x						This question can be explored and "dismantled" through the scoping	5.2 Baltic Sea L2
What are the country level MPA-MSP policy challenges?	x						This question can be explored and "dismantled" through the scoping	5.2 Baltic Sea L2
Which spatial measures are available to meet the 10% strictly protected target?	x						This question can be answered by analysing the legislative framework for the case study area at multiple levels. It can be explored through the scoping	5.2 North Sea L2

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Table A2. Illustrative examples of the ESE1 scoping elements.

Examples of questions related to stakeholders needs (T5.2)	How to design MPA network where VME are well connected in an MSP context?	What are the priority areas for preserving reef-former <i>Lanice conchilega</i> in the Belgian coastal area from climate change effects?	How can deep-water VME be more effectively conserved with regards to anthropogenic impacts arising from human activities in the NW Med	Where are conservation areas for the protection of cetacean to noise pollution, particularly during the breeding and feeding season and in sensitive areas?	How CC can help identify which areas are suitable for oyster restoration? (Reformulation: what areas are suitable for oyster reef restoration in the context of a changing climate?)	How to predict the future of cod and sprat nurseries in the Bay of Gdansk regarding CC?	How to design a climate-smart MPA network	How to protect habitats of priority for conservation in the context of CC	How to maintain population persistence across transboundary MPAs
Main theme of the question, (keywords)	connectivity, vulnerability to human pressures, human use tradeoffs	vulnerability to climate change, climate refugia	vulnerability to human pressures	moving species, sensitivity to noise	climate change sensitivity, restoration	Adaptivity, CC, ecosystem function	climate change sensitivity, connectivity	climate change, habitat conservation	connectivity
A_ Design new MPAs				x	x	x		x	
B_ Enlarging existing MPAs								x	
C_ Manage existing MPAs		x	x					x	x
D_ Design networks	x						x		
Context	MSP	MSP	MSP	MSP	MSP	MSP	MPA	MSP	MPA
Scale (MSP/MPA)									
Geographic area to be defined	*	North Sea (Belgian coasts)	Mediterranean	Mediterranean	North Sea	Baltic	*	*	Mediterranean
Temporal scale to be defined	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Ecological approach (area/species or both)	Area	Species	Area	Area	Area (Both but Area entrance)	Species	Area	Area	Species
Management approach suggested by the question (preferentially keep it toward	selective	selective	selective	selective	selective	selective	selective	selective	selective

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holistic approach)										
Bio-ecological target * need to be defined based on list of species/habitats (D 2.2); ** could be further defined to specific species, communities etc	VME ** (VME can be analysed as general feature or a specific key species of VME can be defined and used as proxy of VME)	reef-former <i>Lanice conchilega</i> (worm)	VME**	cetaceans*	oyster reefs**	cod (Gadus spp.) and sprat (<i>Sprattus</i> spp.)** (nurseries)	*	*	*	
Macro-criteria and potential methodological strategies (to be analysed in the following practices)	Life cycle critical areas /vulnerability (sensitivity) - Traits base approach, ecological connectivity larval dispersal, recruitment, spawning area, life traits (physiological traits, vulnerability to extraction/dredging, pollution),	vulnerability (future distribution and refugia, ecological connectivity)	vulnerability (Life-traits, connectivity, larval dispersal, growth rate, incl. growth pattern, recruitment, spawning area)	vulnerability (Life-traits, connectivity, breeding areas, feeding grounds, foraging areas)	Vulnerability (sensitivity, life traits, Vulnerability, Response of communities to the environment, ecological functioning)	Vulnerability, critical areas for Life cycle (life traits, connectivity criteria e.g. distribution, refuge area, nursery areas),	Vulnerability (response of communities to the environment based on life-traits, ecological functioning, connectivity)	Vulnerability and critical area for life cycle (Refuge areas, Nursery areas)	Critical areas for life cycle (Connectivity, Recruitment, adult movement)	
Human uses *to be defined if relevant; **to be better defined if relevant	*	*	Fishing Industry**	Shipping**	*	*	*	*	*	
Human pressures *to be defined if relevant; **to be better defined if relevant	*	*	*Example: damage/mortality from bottom trawling, ghost nets, plastic pollution	noise**	*	*	*	*	*	